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**SPORTS INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR
AND PARTICIPATION OF PWDs IN NCR**

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12 August 2024

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **EMMALYN P. BAMBA** with the title: **“SPORTS INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR AND PARTICIPATION OF PWDs IN NCR”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

A proud alumna of the University of the Philippines (UP), College of Mass Communication, Emmalyn V. Perez de Tagle-Bamba, or Malyn as she is usually called by friends and colleagues, has always possessed a keen sense for identifying development opportunities. This understanding, and the gift of time during the pandemic, would lead this “Iska” to pursue a Master in Development Communications course at the UP Open University.

Malyn grew up deeply immersed in the sports world, significantly influenced by her father's career as a sports journalist. This early exposure nurtured her passion for sports, and instilled a profound appreciation for the stories that influence the sports community. These laid the groundwork for a career that marries her enthusiasm for sports with her strong interest to serve.

Her tenure as the Head of the then incipient Public Communications Office at the Philippine Sports Commission (PSC), allowed Malyn a close look at para-athletes and para-sports. This opportunity gave her a strong affinity with this sector in the sports community as her work allowed her into the narratives which made them strong, resilient and victorious. For her, they are truly super-human, as they are monikered by a corporate giant -- one of few supporters of para-sports.

Armed with her personal observation in the course of her work, supported by her initial research for a thesis proposal, a significant gap in how PWDs access sports information and its impact on their participation emerged. Seeing the study's potential, she customized her research to see ways to address this gap and, at the same time,

function as a useful advocacy instrument. Her study attempts to underscore how PWD participation rates may be greatly increased by carefully crafting sports content and making it available for them.

With a strong conviction in the transformative power of knowledge and involvement, Malyn hopes this small contribution will help highlight the inclusive and inviting nature of sports for all.

Acknowledgement

A well-known proverb teaches, "It takes a village to raise a child." This wisdom perfectly sums up my thesis, and MDC, journey.

I am profoundly grateful to my "village"—the remarkable group of mentors, colleagues, friends, and family who have provided me unwavering support, encouragement, companionship, faith recharges, fun breaks, coffee, food and invaluable insights throughout this experience. Let me add new acquaintances, new-found contacts, recently discovered, same feathered flock-mates who were all God-sent to make seemingly impossible things, possible.

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I appreciate the trust and help of all my respondents.

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To God be all glory and praise!

Dedication

For Bianca, Renee, Sophie and Raymond.

For Mama Linda and Papa Tito.

For Mama Mary and Jesus.

I hope I make you all proud.

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between the sports information-seeking behavior of persons with disabilities (PWDs) and their participation in sports, as well as identified the barriers which usually hinder them, with a focus on individuals in the National Capital Region (NCR) of the Philippines. The research involved two distinct clusters: sports-inclined and non-sports-inclined PWDs.

A mixed-method approach, following a concurrent triangulation design, was employed.

The findings reveal a weak yet statistically significant positive correlation between active sports information seeking and sports participation among PWDs. Family and friends come out as strong influencers in PWDs' decisions to engage in sports.

The study recommends developing more effective legislation and policies, enhancing information accessibility and availability, and strengthening social support systems to promote inclusivity and increased sports participation among PWDs. Further research is suggested to explore these relationships and contrasts in greater depth and to develop adapted strategies to overcome the identified barriers and improve sports engagement among PWDs.

Keywords: PWDs, Sports Information, Sports Participation, NCR, influences to PWDs

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Say sports and the words wellness and health will come to mind. It is considered one of the foundations of human well-being, along with good nutrition.

No less than the United Nations (UN) has given sports the due recognition of playing a role in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals or the SDGs (Lemke, 2016). Sports is an enabler of sustainable development. (ASEAN, 2022).

One of the many goals it serves to promote, uphold, and support is SDG number three which is to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages. For all – everyone, without exception. Sports in this sense includes the simple act of play and movement.

However, what if that simple capacity to play and move is denied one person in part or in full because of physical limitations due to disabilities?

According to the 2020 Census of Population and Housing (CPH) done by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), there are 8,469,426 persons with functional difficulties/disabilities in the country or 8.7% of the population at that time. (PSA, 2022). It stood at 1.44 Million persons with disabilities (PWD) or 1.57% of the population at the time of the 2010 census. (PSA , 2013).

The 2020 census showed a marked increase to almost 8.5 Million. (PSA, 2022). The sector was not included in the 2015 census. It reflected the very poor attention paid to this marginalized group.

Another reference for the sector is the Philippine Registry of Persons with Disability (PRPG) which is a registry managed by the Department of Health (DOH) and shared to different agencies like the National Council of Disability Affairs (NCDA) and the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). According to the April 8, 2024 version of this registry, there are 1,517,005 registered PWDs across all 17 regions of the country. The region with the most number of registered PWDs are in the National Capital Region (NCR) with 243,095.(Philippine Registry of Persons with Disability, 2024).

PWDs' participation in sports, whether as a hobby, past-time or as a career is significantly lower than people with full physical functions. This is proven in the Philippine setting where only 232 para-athletes are in the national team line-up. This translates to just 14.58 percent of the 1581 national athletes at the elite level of sports in the Philippines (PSC-NSAAO, 2023).

Despite the dismal numbers, the fact remains that physical activity, or indulging in sports, could help them improve their physical well-being. It is for this very reason that they need to indulge in sports, whether at the level of play and movement or at a more active level of sports as a hobby or a career. Quoting the UN: "The universal popularity of sport and its physical, social, and economic development benefits make

it an ideal tool for fostering the inclusion and well-being of persons with disabilities or differently abled.” (UN, N.D.).

This statement also points to another SDG which sports serves to bolster which is SDG number ten, the goal which aims to reduce inequalities within and among countries.

Afacan and Afacan (2021) also said the same thing in their research, suggesting that disability can be reduced or eliminated by removing the socio-structural barriers that exclude and restrict disabled people.

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) recognized this power, and the challenge that faces the people in Southeast Asia, the marginalization of people with disabilities. This is what prompted them to recognize and adopt the ASEAN Parasport Federation (APSF). This federation has been working to fight the stigma and negative perception about PWDs. They are the same organization that created the ASEAN Paragames in 2001. (Wahab, 2023).

In the Philippines, the Philippine Paralympic Committee/ Philippine Sports Association for the Differently Abled (PPC-PHILSPADA), the country representative at the APSF, is working with more PWDs across the different regions of the country, outside of the national team. (Philspada, 2009).

These show a positive development but there are still many challenges facing PWDs in sports. The PPC-Philspada cites that they need more support which cannot be fully placed on the government only, however, the private sector still lacks earnest interest in their sector. (Murillo, 2017).

Corollary to this, not a lot of media coverage has been given to our para sports and athletes, aside from the usual coverage when the national team participates in regional or world events. This limits the information available about and to the sector both in traditional and new media. This situation does not help the natural tendency of the physically challenged to shy away from physically taxing activities like sports. Physical education and sports activities adapted for the disabled should be featured more in the media to increase public awareness on the topic of disability. (Afacan & Afacan, 2021).

Given the foregoing situation, it is fascinating to see how their interest in sports information possibly affect their participation in sports. Does it affect their interest in sports? Does it influence their participation in sports? Does it fuel their drive to stay in sports?

If there is a relation, then it would be one matter to just give a token nod to this sector every now and then. It becomes imperative to put serious effort into making the quality information readily and easily available to them if we are to increase sports participation among the PWDs.

Statement of the Problem

There is an observably low participation in sports among PWDs in the Philippines.

With the aim of increasing their participation, it is vital to know ways that could push more participation in sports among members of this sector.

This study aims to see if sports information-seeking behavior affect the participation of PWDs in sports.

Following are the specific questions the study targets to answer:

1. What is the level of information-seeking behavior of the PWDs in NCR towards sports?
2. What sense-making factors affect the information-seeking behavior of the PWDs in NCR towards sports?
3. What is the level of sports participation among PWDs in NCR?
4. Is there a relation between the PWD's information-seeking behavior and participation in sports in NCR?

Objectives of the Study

In consideration of the chosen topic, this research aims to:

1. Identify the level of sports information-seeking behavior towards sports among PWDs in the NCR.
2. Identify the factors present in the sense-making processes among PWDs in the NCR.

3. Identify the level of sports participation among PWDs in the NCR.
4. Identify if there is a relationship between information-seeking behavior and participation in sports of PWDs in NCR.

Significance of the Study

Sport is recognized to promote well-being and physical fitness in people, especially among PWDs who have unique physical needs. Understanding how PWDs' participation in sports can be improved would be helped by studying the relationship between their sports information seeking behavior and their participation.

There are various challenges that might affect how PWDs perceive their need for information and how to access it. As a result, sports information might not be perceived as a priority.

The knowledge individuals possess greatly affects the way we study, come to decisions or take actions. Therefore, the way PWDs seek information and perceive the need for it is assumed to directly impact their level of sports participation.

With the considerations above, the results of this study will help achieve the following:

- (1) Identify possible factors that inhibit sports participation despite the availability of information.

(2) Present data to share with policymakers and sports administrators about the most effective ways or platforms to engage PWDs and facilitate their involvement in sports.

(3) Provide data that could help increase sports participation among PWDs.

Scope and limitations of the study

The scope of this research is to examine the sports information seeking behavior and participation among persons with disabilities (PWDs), with a focus on two distinct groups: sports-inclined and non-sports-inclined PWDs.

For the sports-inclined group, the research investigated the behavior in seeking sports-related information and their patterns of sports participation by studying respondents from the Philippine National Para-team and members of the Philspada.

On the other hand, for PWDs who do not actively participate in sports, their general information seeking behavior and any barriers to sports participation was explored.

This study focused on respondents coming from the National Capital Region (NCR) due to the substantial response rate from this area. Geographical focus was given to NCR given the number of responses from the area, and also considering time, logistical and budgetary constraints,

This research targeted 100 respondents in both clusters, in order to get information from both ends. While it is helpful to know the challenges hindering sports

participation among PWDs, it would also be helpful to see what worked among those who decided to make sports a big part of their life.

On the non-sports-inclined cluster, while the initial sampling plan was to get responses from all 17 regions of the Philippines, the absence of responses from 7 regions and 64% from NCR comprising the return of responses, prompted the adjustment in sampling scheme mid-way. A further stratification was done to take only the NCR responses for analysis. However, this restricts the study's ability to identify regional variations in information seeking behavior and sports participation and to take into account the many insightful responses from those coming from the other 9 regions with entries.

A survey questionnaire administered via accessible digital platforms (email, social media platforms, chat applications) and a few respond-on-paper gathering were done.

These modes provided a swift gathering of data, however, it also presents limitations in terms of measuring changes in responses over time, the benefit of facial and other non-verbal communication that one gets from face-to-face interviews, or factors that may affect the responses of the participants like ease of access, connectivity or other situational factors.

Also, the reliance on surveys distributed through online platforms or through PWD groups may have influenced the types of respondents who participated. Those

with better access to these groups or those more engaged with social media or online platforms might be potentially overrepresented.

A qualitative approach was also taken to support the numerical data. A focal group discussion with three para-athletes was done along with interviews of key informant persons from the PSC, the NCDA and Philspada.

After the themes were established from among the responses in the FGD and KIPs, it would have been good measure to sit down with them again to validate if they agree with the observed qualitative results and if there were more points they would like to add on the themes and sub-themes gathered. This would make the result stronger and more credible with additional supporting information. A bigger FGD with non-sports inclined respondents would also have been a strong support to both the quantitative and qualitative results.

The study did not distinguish the category of disability the participant has, whether apparent or non-apparent, as categorized by the NCDA. (Bautista, 2021). For as long as their disabilities fall under the categories of the DOH and the WHO, they are considered as PWDs in this research.

As a point of reference, in sports, there is the practice of “classification” which determines if an athlete has a qualified impairment to compete in a sport and dictates how they are going to be grouped together in competition. This practice “levels” the playing field in the matter of their abilities to minimize the impact of their impairment to the competition. This is sport specific. (International Paralympic Committee, n.d.)

This study did not cover categorization of impairment as it does not aim to look at the variables in sports-specific context. Categorization of disability was not scoped since the study was looking at PWDs in general, including those who are involved in the level of play and movement only. Classification in sports happens when they enter official competitions already. However, this could be an off-shoot study to delve deeper into impairment-specific implications of sports information seeking and participation of PWDs.

It considered the communication opportunities they have such as preferred information/communication platforms, and information resources.

The study also looked at the factors which affect their general decision-making as well as sports participation decisions.

The processing of data was carried out with the assistance of a statistician, as advised the researcher. This collaboration ensured a more proficient and rigorous handling of both qualitative and quantitative data. However, it is important to note that while the statistician's expertise greatly enhanced the analytical process, her limited exposure to the full context of the research, particularly the insights from FGD and KII, may have influenced the interpretation of some results.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Review of Related Literature

The World Health Organization (WHO), the United Nations (UN), and several studies all support the belief that sports promote well-being and good health.

Sports not only improves physical well-being, but it also helps reduce the stigma associated with disabilities because it transforms the community attitudes and outlook. (UN, 2011).

The WHO created a global initiative to promote healthy lifestyles and advance health for all through sports and partnerships with the sports community through their Sports for All Programme while the UN has time and again communicated the capacity of sports to promote well-being which supports the attainment of the SDGs. (Tardy,A. nd.). (Gary & Rubin, 2016).

Sports and the SDGs

In 2015, member states of the UN adopted 17 goals they hope to achieve in 15 years. This is called the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development. Item 37 of the UN's publication on the SDGs, Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, recognizes sports as an "important enabler of development." (UN, 2015). The document recognizes the significant "contribution of sport to the realization of development and peace in its promotion of tolerance and respect and the contributions it makes to the empowerment of women and of young

people, individuals and communities as well as to health, education and social inclusion objectives.” (UN, 2015).

Sports in this study shows its might in shoring up SDGs three and ten -- good health and well-being, as well as reducing inequalities respectively.

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations or the ASEAN, in 2023, came up with the Chiang Mai Declaration on strengthening ASEAN-Japan Cooperation on Sports towards 2030. The program aims to attain the SDGs through sports, particularly football since the international federation for the sport, Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) is actively partnered with the UN and the ASEAN on promoting sports for the SDGs. (ASEAN, 2023). This was done in support of the ASEAN Declaration on Leveraging The Role of Sports in ASEAN Community-Building and Achieving The SDGS signed in 2022. (ASEAN, 2022).

The China government established a “Healthy China 2030” program to respond to this call. (Dai, et al, 2020). Canada has a sport support program - Canada Sports Policy as part of their SDG Planned Initiatives. (Canadian Heritage, 2021). Singapore has it integrated in their approach to the 2030 agenda. (Ang, 2022).

PWDs and Sports

In the latest report of the UN on the status of the SDGs, they reiterate the role of the SDGs to serve as a roadmap out of the many challenges that face society today. In the same publication, they also state that in this time of a global health crisis compounding the already difficult situation, the hardest hit are the vulnerable

populations of society. (DISD-UN, 2022). It is undeniable that people with disabilities are among the vulnerable members of our society.

Quoting the UN: “the universal popularity of sport and its physical, social and economic development benefits make it an ideal tool for fostering the inclusion and well-being of persons with disabilities.” (UN, N.D.). The legendary former UN Chairman Kofi Anan in 2002 invoked the right of all to play. According to him this is a basic human right. He recognized the role of sports uniting parties, breaking down inequalities and tackling prejudice. (KofiAnnanFoundation, 2015).

Article 30 of the United Nations Conventions on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities includes sports participation in its focus issue. (NCDA, 2008).

Several studies found that sports participation brings about “enhanced functional capacity, health promotion, relationship development, increased optimism, and inclusion in meaningful life activities and roles.” (Cooper et al., 2009). Sport has been increasingly used by many organizations, including the UN, to push for development (Levermore, 2008).

A study on sports among PWD children said that the tenets of sports medicine for children still hold true for those with disabilities since sports is an important and very accessible modality for improving and maintaining optimal health. (Wilson & Clayton, 2010)

The foregoing establishes the benefits of sports to the overall well-being of people, most especially for PWDs.

Despite the many benefits that sports can provide for individuals with disabilities, such as increased physical fitness, socialization, and self-esteem, many barriers exist that prevent them from participating.

A study shows many constraints to PWDs' sports participation, with their research showing mostly external factors (family and peer pressure), structural (access to the internet, accessibility facilities in libraries, entertainment venues, transportation) and internal constraints (personal biases, insecurities and fears) , hindering PWDs from participating in sports (Darcy, 2020).

Another study revealed that access to sport by people with a disability was a major challenge. Lack of awareness, severity of disability, inadequate funding, poor transport, lack of support from significant others, lack of appreciation of the value of sport, poor and inadequate assistive devices, poor training equipment and the role of the sports trainer were found to be limiting factors to sport participation by PWDs. (Nhamo & Sibanda, 2019).

The foregoing may be factors contributing to the low participation of PWDs in sport among developing countries (Lauff, 2011).

According to Lauff (2011) one major barrier is the lack of accessible facilities and equipment. Most sports venues (inaccessible entrances, lack of wheelchair

ramps, or insufficient equipment for people with sensory or mobility impairments, etc.) and equipment are not designed to accommodate PWDs, making it difficult or impossible for them to participate. In the local setting, the Philippine Sports Commission (PSC) itself tried to provide these facility considerations only in the recent years.

Another challenge cited by Lauff (2011) is the lack of awareness and education about the benefits of sports for PWDs. Many are not aware of the opportunities available to them, or they may have negative perceptions about their ability to participate which can lead to a lack of interest in sports and low participation rates.

The Sports and Development Platform included limited access to information and resources in their list of common barriers facing PWD participation in sports. (SportsandDev, n.d.).

Additionally, economic barriers can limit access to sports for this group as specialized equipment, transportation, and coaching can be costly for many PWDs and their family.

Para Sports In the Philippines

Personal observation of PSC personnel who are part of the agency's different "sports for all" programs like the Laro't Saya sa Parke and Children's Games show very little to no participation among PWDs in the "hobby" or for "occasional physical activity" level of sports participation (Evangelista, personal communication, 7 February 2023).

Evangelista's observation points to location of venue, absence of accessibility ramps, PWD friendly facilities and lack of promotion which appeal to this sector as possible factors of this "lack" of participation.

Information Need and Use

Information is defined as "the attribute inherent in and communicated by one of two or more alternative sequences or arrangements of something (such as nucleotides in DNA or binary digits in a computer program) that produce specific effects" (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). There is an outcome that a series of symbols aim for.

While their work differs a bit, Kundu (2017) relates that Hasaan Shera, a librarian and information scientist, defined information as "a message, a signal or a stimulus that possesses a response potential." Davies (1976), on the other hand, defined information as data that is processed into a form that has meaning to the recipient and is seen as something valuable that might be useful in future decisions or actions. Both look at a future action because of information.

These definitions show that information results in future actions from a processed group of data. In order to process these data, they need to be sought and gathered. They need to "need." Here comes in "information seeking." The way it is sought brings in the behavior aspect of the process or "information seeking behavior."

There has been a slew of works tackling information seeking behavior, from many angles. Most interesting to this topic is the sense-making of people which has

been studied by many scholars and has evolved as the studies on information behavior go further.

The sense-making theory of Dervin looks at information seeking as “verbing” or the active search for information. Once information is acquired, a bridge is formed over a gap, to connect the contextual to an outcome.

Dervin’s model consists of four elements:

1. A **situation** in which information problems arise;
2. A **gap**, which identifies the difference between the contextual situation and the desired situation an outcome
3. The **consequences of the information seeking and sense-making process**, and
4. A **bridge** or a way to close the gap between situation and outcome (Kundu, 2017)

This research tries to look at the “gap” (sports information) between the situation (disability) and the “desired outcome” (sports participation) and how both ends can meet “as a consequence of” the information-seeking and sense-making process.

Connected to this is the theory of Marcia Bates, called Berrypicking, where people search for information in bits and pieces, continuously reformulating and refocusing. (Bates, 1989).

Similar studies have been found, like the study of Ginis, et.al, (2021) on the participation of people living with disabilities in physical activity: a global perspective which says that almost around 62 percent of PWDs meet challenges in participating in sports and are at higher risk of health complications due to inactivity than those without disabilities. The study concludes that observation about mainstream health journals' bias against publishing information on PWDs as they think their readers are uninterested in the topic (Ginis, et al, 2021).

A similar (or related) study is "How Information-Seeking Behavior, Essential Technologies, and Resilience Enhance the Academic Performance of Students" which found that information seeking has a positive and significant effect on the academic performance of post-graduate students in three universities in Pakistan. (Miraj et al., 2021). The same study also noted a positive effect of information seeking behavior, IT ability, reading and writing capacities and resilience capabilities on the performance of students. The relationship found in this study on the effect of information seeking to the positive result is a relationship that is similarly pursued by this research.

Results from the Philippines' 2022 report card on physical activity for children and adolescents concluded that despite efforts, the Philippines fail at reaching a standard level of physical activity among this age group (Cagas, et al, 2022). One can only surmise, given the lack of solid information, that this situation would be worse among PWDs at least in the same age range.

Another study which gave light on the relevance of information seeking behavior said that "information-seeking is a means not an end. It is insufficient merely

to examine the provision of information. It is necessary to understand the context in which the information is sought, the stage in the help-seeking process and the purpose to which it will be used” (Couples, 2002).

The aforementioned study focused on another marginalized sector – women. This wisdom, however, holds for other focuses as well. However, there was no study found specific on the link between sport information need and use of Filipino PWDs.

Factors That Push Sports Participation

Martin & Vitaly (2014) said in their research that parental encouragement was found to have a relation to physical ability perceptions of the youth. In the same study it was also found that a sense of connectedness encouraged a more active participation in sports for those youth who are involved in school sport disability program.

Petrola (2017) said that Paralympics can be a venue for recognition of the rights and dignity of persons with disabilities (PWDs) in the Philippines by providing opportunities to gain self-confidence, self-respect, and self-esteem, which are necessary for achieving self-realization and autonomy.

A study in the Malaysian setting showed that PWDs’ sports participation is affected by the absence of social support, unfavorable public attitudes, inadequate facilities and accessibilities, personal health conditions, financial constraints, and perceived difficulties are some of the factors that make physical activity and sports participation challenging. (Eng et al., 2021). The same study submitted the

recommendation for the public, media and the authority to assist the sector to be treated fairly by creating awareness among the public.

Theoretical Constructs

This study is guided by Dervin's sense-making approach. Dervin was a professor of Communication at Ohio University and held a PhD in communication research. Her interest in the media and the urban poor led to the creation of this theory which focused on the sense-making and sense-unmaking of individuals.

Information-seeking behavior in this context will be better understood from the point of view of sense-making. According to this theory, information-seeking behavior is a process that happens in response to an imbalance in an individual's sense of reality. An individual searches for information to help them make sense of their environment.

The theory says that people engage in an ongoing process of information-seeking and use to make sense of their environment. This involves identifying the information needed to bridge the gap, accessing relevant information sources, evaluating and interpreting the information, and applying the information to the situation obtained. (Dervin, 1983). information is not something that exists apart from human behavioral activity but is created at a specific moment in time-space by one or more humans because it is a matter of self-construction. (Dervin, 1992). It also assumes that reality is not complete or constant but filled with "gaps" (Dervin, 1983).

This theory, in the information-seeking behavior perspective, focuses on “verbings” or on what people do, the reasons, and how they do it (Spurgin, 2006). The individual is considered as the “expert” in his own world. It is often said that the best person to be you is you, and this same logic applies to this assumption of sense-making which ultimately affects the information-seeking behavior of people and how they act on the said information.

As people make “sense” or try to understand something, they also create ideas to bridge the gap between the situation and the looked-forward to “use.” Dervin sees that information is not an object that goes on a linear journey from sender to receiver. Rather it is a process, of seeking information, creating meaning, and eventually gap-building.

In her paper: An overview of sense-making research: Concepts, methods, and results. Paper (1983) Dervin presented a simple illustration of her sense-making approach that may be applied for research:

Figure 1.

Diagram of Dervin’s Sense-making Theory (Dervin, 1983)

SITUATIONS-----GAPS-----USES

In 1987 another illustration of this theory was submitted by Dervin and Clark which already indicated the “bridge over the gap” connecting the situation and outcome/use.

Figure 2.

Diagram of Dervin's Sense-making Theory (Dervin & Clark, 1987)

A good observation on this theory was forwarded by Godbold (2006) saying that the “gap” is both a negative and a positive. It serves as both a barrier to sense-making and a prompt to action to undertake information seeking.

Conceptual Framework

The gap that this study addresses is the perceived need for or lack of sports info. It is this gap that stimulates the need to seek information.

Using the lens of Dervin's sense-making theory, below is the visual representation of the conceptual framework:

Figure 3.

*Sports information seeking by PWDs and its connection to their sports participation
adapted from Brenda Dervin's Sense-Making Theory.*

Information seeking and use are posited as "constructing" activities--as personal creating of sense, thus the individual is making their own senses of information or interpreting. Eventually, they will also create a resulting activity.

This 'interpreting' includes perceiving and making meaning of the gathered information. It is in this phase where many factors come into play. Dervin calls it "verbings" or the actions that people do based on their overall perception of how they should act. In Dervin's theory, there is the influence of space and time at the moment of decision.

The final stage is the outcome, which is the individual's revised sense of reality, in this case, hopefully, sports participation. This revised sense of reality is what the individual uses to respond to the problem that caused the gap in knowledge or understanding.

A part of the study of Agarwal (2012) reflects the suitability of this theory on the objective of this study – it bridges two types of theories (substantive and metatheories) as it also looks for bridges (possible or unseen) over the gap, between the situation and the yearned-for outcome.

Variables

Following this framework, the variables considered in this research are:

Table 1.

Variables in the contextual framework

SITUATION	Persons with disabilities	Independent Variable
GAP	Physical limitations Lack of knowledge/information on sports	Mediating Variables
BRIDGE	Information on sports to teach them how they can engage in physical activities Sports Information Seeking	Mediating Variables
USE	Sports participation	Dependent Variable

Operational Definition of Variables

In this study, the above-mentioned identified variables take on the following operational definitions:

Persons with Disabilities (PWD) – (Independent Variable) refer to people with apparent and non-apparent disabilities as defined by Republic Act 7277 “defined as a person suffering from restriction or different abilities, as a result of a mental, physical or sensory impairment, to perform an activity in a manner or within the range considered normal for a human being. As consistently used in the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons or RA 7277, the sector is referred to as disabled persons. An article by the Ateneo Special Education Society explained that the politically correct term for the sector is “person with disability.” (Alarcon, et al. 2021). This is the term consistently used in this study.

Disability - shall mean (1) a physical or mental impairment that substantially limits one or more psychological, physiological, or anatomical functions of an individual or activities of such individual; (2) a record of such an impairment; or (3) being regarded as having such an impairment.” It is the initial situation/condition or context of being a person with disability, as regarded in our study.

Functional difficulty – (Mediating Variable) also refers to disability in this study as described above. These are the barriers or challenges faced by PWDs, which include physical limitations and lack of knowledge or information about sports.

Sports Information – (Mediating Variable) These are information or resources needed to possibly overcome the gap. In this case, it's the information on sports that can help PWDs learn how to engage in physical activities.

Sports Information Seeking – (Mediating Variable) intentional actions to gain information on sports

Sports participation – (Dependent Variable) refers to involvement in any physical activity/exertions like play and movement or sports, at any level. In this study's conceptual framework, it is taken as the result or use after overcoming the gap.

Sports – used in this research to include play and movement or physical activities as a pastime, exercise, hobby or a career.

Hypotheses of the Study

It is hypothesized that there is a connection between the level of sports information seeking of PWDs and their sports participation.

H1: PWDs who actively seek sports information have a higher likelihood of participating in sports (at any level).

H2: PWDs' information seeking behavior is influenced by other factors on top of which are family, community, and friends.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This study used a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches to examine the behavior of people seeking information about sports and participation among persons with disabilities (PWDs).

Research Design

The research is divided into two clusters: sports-inclined and non-sports-inclined PWDs. This clustering aims to provide a broader understanding of the similarities and differences in behavior and participation patterns among respondents in these two groups and identify factors that affect their decision-making regarding sports information and participation.

Multi-stage sampling was carried out for both clusters.

A mixed methods approach was employed for this study, combining both quantitative and qualitative data through a concurrent triangulation design process. As explained by Creswell and Creswell (2018), this method produces well-balanced findings which provides a deeper understanding of the topic. This method was used to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the research problem by comparing quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings. Comparing these data helped to corroborate and validate results and gave deeper understanding in examining relationships among variables. (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

A quantitative study with a correlational approach was conducted to find the relationship between PWDs' information-seeking behavior and their participation in sports. A survey questionnaire was distributed both online and via traditional printed forms.

To support the quantitative data gathered, deepen the understanding, and establish the narratives on the experiences of the respondents on the subject matter, a qualitative approach was implemented via focus group discussions with selected national para-athletes and interviews with key informants from the PSC, NCDA, and Philspada.

This methodology effectively supports the study of the sports information-seeking behavior and participation of PWDs in NCR. By collecting and analyzing data from both the sports-inclined and non-sports-inclined clusters simultaneously, analyzing it separately and then side-by-side, the research was able to identify points of divergence or convergence between the two data sets by comparing or contrasting the results from each cluster. This approach helped validate the results. Through this, the research provides a deeper understanding of the factors influencing PWDs' engagement with sports in the NCR.

The Locale of the Study

According to the Philippine Registry for Persons with Disability (PRPD) data as of April 18, 2024 the National Capital Region (NCR) has the highest number of PWDs among the 17 regions. (Philippine Registry for Persons with Disability, 2024).

Respondents of the non-sports-inclined cluster were from the NCR, gathered randomly from NCDA and DSWD connected offices.

For the sports-inclined cluster, members of the national team and the Philspada were taken as respondents. They train at PSC-controlled sports complexes in Pasig and Manila cities, therefore they were also taken as respondents from the NCR.

Overall, all the respondents are assured to be coming from one region. In the above-mentioned PRPD as of 8 April 2024, which gathered 1,517,005 total PWD count in the country, the NCR had the highest number with 243,095 counted at 16.02% of the population. (Philippine Registry for Persons with Disability, 2024).

It is worth noting that a bigger scope of respondents would have given stronger results to help us better understand relationships among different variables.

It would also give us a glimpse into regional differences or similarities which could be useful in understanding relationships and how to maximize these differences when crafting communication plans for this sector.

Respondents of the Study

The study considered any people with challenges, in whatever category. According to Republic Act 7277, also known as the Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities, PWDs are those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments that may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.

This study aligned with the World Health Organization's International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health's (ICF) usual use of categories such as: (1) physical disability, (2) visual, (3) hearing, and (4) speech impairment, (5) intellectual disability, and (6) psychosocial disability. (World Health Organization, 2001).

Categories observed and recognized by our Department of Health and the NCDA are consistent with this.

Sampling Scheme

Figure 4.

Two-staged Stratified Sampling Design of the Respondents.

The study took a multi-stage stratified sampling design, specifically two-staged. The population was divided into two stratified groups: sports-inclined and non-sports-inclined. Under these two groups, another stratification process was employed. For

sports inclined, respondents were chosen randomly from organization membership of the Philspada and members of the national para-team.

The initial plan for the target respondents for the non-sports-inclined cluster faced some challenges affecting the completion of data gathering. To address this, the proponent sought the assistance of the NCDA in gathering data for this cluster. The NCDA was very generous to assist, through their Department of Social Welfare and Development partners. The plan shifted to gathering data from all 17 regions of the country.

However, midway through, an unequal distribution of respondents was observed with results skewed towards more respondents coming from one region at 53% during that time. Another stratification in the sampling was decided on, to focus on NCR responses which at the final stage reached 73 responses or accounting for 64% of the total.

Although the targeted 75 was not reached for this cluster, the final 73 is close enough, with the 101 of the other cluster making up for it.

Using the G*Power calculation for sample sizing with a confidence level of 95%, an accepted margin of error of 5%, and an effect size of 28.50%, the sample size must need to be at least 149. However, due to having two stratified groups, the final sample size must be divisible by 2, hence the final size is at least 150. Consequently, the two stratified groups must have at least 75 respondents. This is in consideration of the target respondents' response, calculated from a projected 60% response rate.

Overall, the research studied 174 respondents, exceeding the minimum 150 planned sample size.

Research Instrument

A seven-part survey questionnaire was designed to collect data on the possible relationship between PWDs' sports information-seeking preferences, sense-making factors, and their sports participation. The instrument had close-ended questions and a few open-ended questions in the end as a way to cross-check data from the guided response questions. The first section was composed of statements seeking the state of the respondents' information-seeking preferences about sports. These statements reflect factors on the sense-making of the respondents which the researcher wants to analyze. The second section of the questionnaire had statements assessing their sports participation.

The questionnaire gathered data that showed the attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors of the participants concerning their decision-making. (Librero, 2011).

A focus group discussion with three national para-athletes was conducted. This gave the researcher direct information on what factors helped them decide to become athletes and provided a glimpse of their experiences as PWDs in sports. The course of questions and topics followed the same items included in the questionnaire. Interviews with key informant persons from the PSC, NCDA, and the Philspada were also conducted to further support the FGD results and quantitative data.

Data Gathering Procedures

The study was administered through a questionnaire sent online and via traditional printed-out forms for some, distributed via City Social Work Offices or partner groups, given the limitations in capacity, time, logistics, and resources.

For the focus group discussion, an online meeting was conducted via the Zoom platform. For the key informant person interviews, two were conducted face to face (PSC and NCD) and one via the Zoom platform (Philspada).

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics were observed during the data gathering process.

Data privacy and confidentiality of the information shared by the participants for both survey-questionnaire and focus group discussions were handled with utmost care. The purpose of gathering, as well as the manner of handling of information, were clearly laid out in the forms, both digital and printed-out versions.

For the FGDs and KIP interviews, permission to record the exchanges were acquired by the researcher and granted by the resource persons.

Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the analysis of the quantitative data gathered.

Descriptive statistics was employed in determining the level of information-seeking behavior of the participants towards sports and the sense-making factors this behavior entailed. Basic descriptive values such as frequency, percentage, median, mode, and standard deviation were evaluated to understand further the assessment of the observed variables. Frequency and percentage were used as measures for summary data of the basic responses of the respondents in demographic profiling and numerous categorical questions. The median and mode are for averaging the overall information-seeking behavior and sense-making factors to produce the overall representation among the PWDs in NCR. On the other hand, standard deviation showed the variation among the answers of respondents, if individual responses deviate from the overall representation evaluated or not. Given the descriptive nature of the summary statistics involved under this, there is no required minimum sample size for them to be used.

Additionally, inferential statistics was done to measure the correlation between the PWDs' information-seeking behavior and participation in sports given that the sample size reached the minimum target number. Spearman Rho Correlation Test is the specific parametric test used as the data to be gathered are in ranked levels or ordinal sets. For this, the researcher employed a 95% significance level with only a 5% allowable margin of error. Given this process of setting parameters for decision-making for the hypothesis, the computed minimum sample size of 150 was followed. Statistical software was used, specifically, SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences).

Table 2.

Correlation Coefficient and Their Respective Interpretations for Spearman Rho Results.

Correlation coefficient	Interpretation
$r = 0.0$	No correlation
$0.0 < r < 0.2$	Very weak correlation
$0.2 < r < 0.4$	Weak Correlation
$0.4 < r < 0.6$	Moderate Correlation
$0.6 < r < 0.8$	High correlation
$ r > 0.8$	Very high correlation

As to the qualitative aspect, thematic analysis was employed using the qualitative statistical software of MAXQDA to generate the coding book. According to Braun and Clarke (2013), thematic analysis is a method that helps identify and analyze patterns within a qualitative data set. The researcher believes that thematic analysis is appropriate for this portion due to its flexible nature regarding data analysis. Following the six phases of thematic analysis, the researcher familiarized herself with the given data by transcribing the interview in the FGD and KIP. Afterward, the patterns found were collated into themes and were reviewed. A total of six respondents were gathered for the focus group discussion and key informant interviews. Given the qualitative nature, there is no targeted minimum sample size as well for this.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following are data collected and sorted from the quantitative research done via distribution of a questionnaire, followed by the thematic analysis done on the qualitative research done through FGD and KIP interviews.

The stories of our para-athletes are wrought with experiences of sacrifice, hardship and overcoming. This researcher's FGD with them contain enough materials that can produce several inspiring books and tales of victory through sports. Each of these para-athletes is a living witness to the transformative power of sports, and the power of information in bringing them to the shores of their present athletic achievements.

The results of this research matched their experience with evidentiary support. While there are a number of factors that affect a PWD's decision to participate in sports, availability and his access to sports information are shown to be directly related to his sports participation.

Results supported both hypotheses which drove this research.

In the following discussion, for brevity, sports-inclined cluster will be referred to as SI and the non-sports-inclined cluster as NSI.

Detailed data of the results and additional analyses are available in the Annexes.

There is Interest in Sports Among PWDs

It is notable though that among the non-sports inclined, there is neutral interest to join sports getting only a median of 3, as opposed to the very strongly agreeing result from the sports inclined group getting a median of 5 in a range of answers between 1 (lowest level of interest) to 5 (highest level of interest). (Annex A, Table 8)

The first theme formed in the qualitative research portion of this study supports this finding as it shows an interest among PWDs to be involved in sports. (Annex C)

Some of the notable codes gathered were:

- "There are people interested, but we had to really come up with money to be able to pay for their transportation."
- "Although they like the idea about this, not all of them will be able to get there."
- "Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work."
- "There are people that wanted to... but you had a market, but you had people that wanted to."

Following that result, it was observed that among the non-sports inclined, majority have an involvement at the level of play and movement only (second lowest rank to none/no involvement) with most of them saying they choose "not applicable" in the length of time they were involved in sports. For the other group, it was a natural

majority leaning towards involvement in the career-level, with most of them saying they have been in sports between 5 to 10 years. (Annex A, Tables 9 and 10)

Those Active in Sports Make Time

Among the sports inclined 95.05% say they actively seek sports information, 52.4752% seek sports information daily, and majority of them (54.4554%) allot 1 to 2 hours a day consuming sports information. Among those in the other cluster, there was still a majority (61.6438%) who actively seek sports information although at a lower percentage than the SI cluster. The NSI side also consumes sports information at a lesser frequency at once a month or less for the majority (28.7671%) and if measured in hours in a day, that would be only about ½ an hour. (Annex A, Tables , 12 and 13)

As could be gleaned from the data above, the sports-inclined cluster showed a higher interest in sports information, actively sought it and allotted more time and frequency consuming it.

Table 3.

Bar Graph of Respondents' Frequency of Conscious (Actively Sought) Interaction with Sports information

Information is Part of Their Decision to be In Sports

When asked if sports information affected their decision whether to participate in sports or not, both groups had a majority of yes answer (NSI- 75.34%; SI-73.27%), with 31% of the SI side confirming that it was an actual part of their decision-making. Both clusters also said that sports information inspired them to join sports, but was later on discouraged by either their family, friends or community (NSI-70%; SI-46%). (Annex A, Tables 14 and 15)

Connection Found

The first hypothesis – PWDs who actively seek sports information have a higher likelihood of participating in sports (at any level) – was validated by the data gathered

and analyzed, as can be seen in the foregoing. It is further strengthened by the correlational testing done between different variables.

Table 4.

Spearman Rho Correlation Testing between the PWD's Information-seeking Behavior and Level of Participation in Sports in NCR wherein The Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information as Independent Variable

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Do you actively seek sports information?	With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports?	0.3983	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
Do you actively seek sports information?	What is your level of sports participation?	0.3475	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
Do you actively seek sports information?	For how long have you been active in sports?	0.1780	0.0188	Very Weak Positive	Significant

Table 4 positions the results for the correlational testing employed between the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of actively seeking sports information and the level of their participation in sports in NCR, using the Spearman Rho as the data are treated in ordinal or ranked level. As shown, the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of actively seeking sports information have significant relationships in all the factors of level of participation in sports such as the interest in participating sports, sports participation and length of being active in sports, given that all of their

p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = 0.0188, < 0.001$). Specifically in describing the type of relationships they have, the level of actively seeking sports information and level of interest in participating in sports have a weak positive relationship. Positive relationship means direct relationship wherein the movement of the two variables involved are in the same manner. And the weak aspect constitutes the degree of manners of the relationship. With that, this means that as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Further, the level of actively seeking sports information and level of sports participation have weak positive relationships as well. This signifies that as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the level of sports information of the respondents also increases in a weak manner.

Lastly, the level of actively seeking sports information and length of being active in sports have weak positive relationships. This means that as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases in a weak manner.

The following visually represents the data above.

Figure 5.

Scatter Plotting between the Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information and Interest in Participating in Sports

Figure 5 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the level of actively seeking sports information and interest in participating in sports. As shown, as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 6.

Scatter Plotting between the Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information and Sports Participation

Figure 6 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the level of actively seeking sports information and sports participation. As shown, as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the sports participation also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 7.

Scatter Plotting between the Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information and Length of being Active in Sports

Figure 7 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the level of actively seeking sports information and length of being active in sports. As shown, as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases but in a very weak manner.

Table 5.

Spearman Rho Correlation Testing between the PWD's Information-seeking Behavior and Level of Participation in Sports in NCR wherein the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a Day as Independent Variable

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours)	With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports?	0.3410	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours)	What is your level of sports participation?	0.2798	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours)	For how long have you been active in sports?	0.1785	0.0185	Very Weak Positive	Significant

Table 5 depicts the results for the correlational testing employed between the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of length of consumption of sports information in a day and the level of their participation in sports in NCR, using the Spearman Rho as the data are treated in ordinal or ranked level. As shown, the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of length of consumption of sports information in a day have significant relationships in all the factors of level of participation in sports such as the interest in participating sports, sports participation and length of being active in sports, given that all of their p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = 0.0021, < 0.001$). Specifically in describing the type of relationships they have, the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of interest in participating in sports have a weak positive relationship. Positive relationship means direct relationship wherein the movement of the two variables involved are in the same manner. The weak aspect constitutes the degree of manners of the relationship. With that, this means that as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Moreover, the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of sports participation have weak positive relationships as well. This signifies that as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the level of sports information of the respondents also increases in a weak manner.

Lastly, the length of consumption of sports information in a day and length of being active in sports have a very weak positive relationship. This means that as the

length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the length of being active in sports also increases in a very weak manner. The above is visually portrayed below.

Figure 8.

Scatter Plotting between the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a day and Level of Interest in Participating in Sports

Figure 8 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of interest in participating in sports. As shown, as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the level of interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 9.

Scatter Plotting between the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a day and Sports Participation

Figure 9 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of sports participation. As shown, as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the level of sports participation also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 10.

Scatter Plotting between the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a day and Length of being Active in Sports

Figure 10 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the length of consumption of sports information in a day and length of being active in sports. This

shows that as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the length of being active in sports also increases but in a very weak manner.

Table 6.

Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between the PWD's Information-seeking Behavior and Level of Participation in Sports in NCR wherein Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information as Independent Variable

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought) interaction with sports information	With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports?	0.3879	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought) interaction with sports information	What is your level of sports participation?	0.3571	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought) interaction with sports information	For how long have you been active in sports?	0.1626	0.0320	Very Weak Positive	Significant

Table 6 demonstrates the results for the correlational testing employed between the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of frequency of interaction with sports information and the level of their participation in sports in NCR, using the Spearman Rho as the data are treated in ordinal or ranked level. As shown, the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of frequency of interaction with sports information have significant relationships in all the factors of level of participation in sports such as the interest in participating sports, sports participation and length of being active in sports, given that all of their p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = < 0.001$).

Specifically in describing the type of relationships they have, the frequency of interaction with sports information and level of interest in participating in sports have a weak positive relationship. Positive relationship means direct relationship wherein the movement of the two variables involved are in the same manner. And the weak aspect constitutes the degree of manners of the relationship. With that, this means that as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Moreover, the frequency of interaction with sports information and level of sports participation has weak positive relationships as well. This signifies that as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the level of sports information of the respondents also increases in a weak manner. Lastly, the frequency of interaction with sports information and length of being active in sports have a very weak positive relationship. This means that as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases in a very

Following is the visual representation of the above in scatter plotting.

Figure 11.

Scatter Plotting between the Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information and Level of Interest in Participating in Sports

Figure 11 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the frequency of interaction with sports information and level of interest in participating in sports. As shown, as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the level of interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 12.

Scatter Plotting between the Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information and Sports Participation

Figure 12 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between frequency of interaction with sports information and level of sports participation. As shown, as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the level of sports participation also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 13.

Scatter Plotting between the Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information and Length of being Active in Sports

Figure 13 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the frequency of interaction with sports information and length of being active in sports.

As shown, as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases but in a very weak manner.

As can be seen in the figures above, relationship between actively seeking sports information, its consumption and interest in sports, and sports participation is definitely present.

Further research which could gather a bigger sample and afford the implementation of a more rigid methodology can possibly show a stronger relationship between these factors. For this research, it was enough to show their direct relationship with statistical significance.

Sports Information Got them into Sports and Helps Get them to Stay

A notable result was 95.0495% among the sports-inclined cluster agree that sports information was a factor in pushing them to participate in sports. (Annex A, Table 14). For the NSI, it was also notable that 93.1507% also said that it was a factor, although this could not apply fully to them as most do not participate in sports. Connecting it with their strong opinion on the importance of sports for PWDs, their push for PWDs to get into sports, one could assume that sports information would also be a factor should they decide to go into sports.

Going further, qualitative information showed that sports information did not only get them into sports, but it also helped them stay in sports.

2024 Paris Paralympic qualifier, Ernie Gawilan of swimming shared that as an athlete, he tries to supplement his physical training with new knowledge he gets from social media. He said that with the help of Youtube, he is able to learn about techniques that help him better his performance. His medal haul shows there is truth in this as he continues to reap victories for the country despite his physical limitations and challenges in funding and resources. He said that for him, information is very important because people, not only PWDs, must try to enrich themselves and grow whatever talents they had

The other two interviewees also say they get supplemental information from the sports information they consume, as well as keeping them inspired.

Both hypotheses were shown true in this story of one of our FGD interviewees. Three-time Paralympian, and recent qualifier to the 2024 Paris Paralympics, Jerrold Mangliwan shared that while his friends were instrumental in getting him into sports, reading about the other athletes and learning about the skills and talents needed in sports, gave him more push to try it and stay in it. This comes from a person who was stricken with polio as a child, because the city health officer would only open a vaccine vial for two kids and he was the only kid in their small, mountainous Kalinga neighborhood. He could have easily turned into a bitter person given the sorry situation which came to him because of the City Health Officer's poor choices. Mangliwan said that his perseverance and positive outlook in life despite his disability which could have been avoided with just half a vaccine shot came from the support of his family and being aware of the many opportunities that sports opened for him. If

one meets Mangliwan in person, exudes an air of peace, strength, leadership and authority that one could easily forget he is sitting in a wheelchair.

Family Tops Main Influences on Decisions

This research also projected in its second hypothesis that PWD's information seeking behavior is influenced by other factors, on top of which are family, community and friends.

It is worth noting that family and friends were consistent replies in the top three answers for (1) deciding to do anything, (2) trying something new, or (3) making choices in life. (Annex A, Tables 15, 16 and 17) In all three decision moments the family topped the replies of both groups. Both groups ranked family and friends as the first and second factors when deciding to do anything or trying something new. Both factors were still in the top three answers to the question about factors in making life choices with personal knowledge as a 3rd choice for non-sports inclined group and social opinion as the third rank among the sports-inclined.

Family and friends also emerged as influential factors to the interviewees when they went into sports. This shows the crucial position of these influences in a person's sense-making of information, decisions and actions.

Highlighting the impact of family, friends and community to one's perception and eventual decisions, the story shared by one of our athlete interviewees is remarkable. One of them grew up being brushed-off as someone who will not go anywhere, being a paraplegic and confined to the floors of their small nipa hut. She

said that because of her disability, even her father shunned her and would hide her in the house. "He was embarrassed to bring me out in public." Their neighbors would often shame her and tell her that she will not amount to anything and will not go anywhere. Only her mother would care for her. In adulthood, her friends and her husband later introduced her to sports and gave her the financial and moral support to try it. Jesebel Tordesillas-Suarez later became the country's consistent medalist in para-athletics, winning both a silver in Javelin throw and a bronze in Discus throw in the 2023 ASEAN Paragames in Cambodia. Her story shows how powerful the influence of family and friends is on one's own perception of self and in the decisions they take in life.

Peso-Driven Decisions

An additional factor which emerged to influence decisions to join sports is money. Our PWDs face the challenge of money/funding/economics/work which emerged as a common theme in the interviews, supported by the narrative replies of our respondents citing their need to work/earn/feed their family/support themselves a major hindrances in their entry to sports. (Annex A, Table 31 and Annex C).

Following are notable codes drawn from the qualitative data:

- "Lack of funding is really a problem, especially when they compete abroad. Because if there is funding, it would be easier for them."
- "Awareness is the way to reach out to them. The downside is yes we have awareness, but then next is their question if they will get support."

- "The challenge is their common question if they will get support, like those coming from the provinces who will not be supported by LGUs."
- "The need for money is real we cannot deny that. But the love for sports is also real. It must be balanced."
- "Also, the money I get from sports helps my family a lot."
- "There are people interested, but we had to really come up with money to be able to pay for their transportation."
- "Although they like the idea, not all of them will be able to get there."
- "Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work."
- When we formed it and I was asked by President Ramos to put together a national sports organization and linked up with the Olympic Committee, and so that we can be also provided funding. Obviously a very important requirement in being able to develop this part of sports or any sport for that matter.
- "Meaning to say, it has to do also with maybe all Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work. Work is more important than play or sport. Putting food on the table is the priority."

From the open-ended questions in the questionnaire, following are interesting replies related to this:

- I am a tricycle driver
- "I am busy earning money"/ "I have to work."
- "Not enough money"

Related demographics from the questionnaire replies show that the majority of respondents from both groups come from families with a 14,000 and below monthly income. (Annex A, Table 20).

Aside from proving the two hypotheses, data also provided other interesting information.

Awareness Is Key

The main theme of 'Significance of Progressing Sports Information for Higher Sports Participation' emerged. The subtheme of the “Increasing the Visibility of PWDs in Sports by Raising Awareness” was highly noticeable, as all interviewees mentioned it.

Philspada’s Barredo explained that “we have to work for them to know about sports.” He also said that once awareness is created, participation is likely to increase, as he observed.

Both Gawilan and Mangliwan said information is “important/a big deal” for them, before getting into sports and as athletes.

NCDA’s Ortega said that “when the information is readily available publicly, it is easier to participate.”

PSC's Iroy gave a good tip for national agencies and entities of national scope: "Awareness must be given to the public to ensure that person with disabilities are given support. Our information campaign for awareness must be on a national level." (Annex C)

Connected to this is another interesting matter raised by the athletes in the FGD. Following awareness, is more support. When the concerned agencies or groups are aware of the need, more people offer support. Support in kind, considerations, policies, and money. As the support pours in, increased participation is gained as programs and actions can now be afforded. For those already in sports, better performance is delivered as athletes are able to focus on their sport. (Annex C)

Sports Information Must Be Made Available

Both groups studied agree that (1 &2) sports information is beneficial and useful for PWDs, (3) think that there is enough sports information for PWDs, (4) that sports information must be made more available to PWDs, (5) that sports information encouraged them to participate in sports despite discouragement from family, friends and community. (Annex A, Tables 15, 21 to 24)

A sub-theme which came out of the qualitative research shows a common opinion that sports information is not enough, as opposed to the results of it being enough in the quantitative data. (Annex C)

Both results in the quantitative and qualitative data, however, show a unified sentiment that sports information must be made more available to PWDs. (Annex A, Table 23; Annex C).

Barriers for Sports Participation

Aside from money or funding, following are challenges which face PWDs in participating in sports: (Annex A, Table 30 and Annex C)

- Physical limitations
- Mobility
- Family unwillingness
- Lack of awareness/ information
- Lack of visible role models
- Lack of strong leadership structure (private and government)

Preferred Platform for Sports-Information

The preferred platform among the respondents in both groups is social media, followed by news and broadcast platforms. (Annex A, Table 25).

In the interviews, all of them commented that there is not enough exposure for PWD athletes, para sports and related information. They also highlighted the importance of having role models people can relate to. (Annex C)

The ease of access and availability of social media were top considerations among our interviewees, saying that “English kasi sa iba, sa FB taglish at may video,

naiintindihan ko” and “mas madalas din kasi ako sa celfone, basta may signal lang ok na.” (Annex C)

Everyone Agrees, Sports For All

Despite the disparity in their level and length of involvement in sports, both groups strongly recommend sports to other PWDs, and that they think sports information must be more available to PWDs. (Annex A, Tables 25 and 26). It was notable that the slight difference in the standard deviation of their replies on recommending sports information to other PWDs, the sports-inclined group showed a more solid positive reply given the lower deviation that came out.

In the respondents’ replies to open-ended questions, health topped the reasons they would join sports or why they joined sports, showing that whether one is in sports or not, everyone recognizes the benefits of sports to everyone, especially the PWDs. (Annex A, Tables 31 and 32)

The qualitative data also showed other themes which direct attention to additional efforts which may be made for PWDs aside from furthering sports information such as the need for better organizational support, reliable leadership, long term planning and sustainability of programs as well as the benefits of role model visibility. (Annex C)

Demographics

As a reference for the foregoing information, the demographics of our quantitative respondents are shown below:

Table 7.

Summary of Respondents' Demographics

Information	Distribution	Non-Sports Inclined	Sports Inclined
Age Group	Majority	Ages 46-50 and 51+ (28)	Ages 41-45 (18)
	Least	Ages 8-13 and 20-25 (3)	Ages 26-30 (6)
Gender	Majority	Female (47)	Male (62)
	Least	Male (26)	Female (39)
Educational Level	Majority	College Graduates (26) SPED Prevocational and Vocational Course (1 each)	College Graduates (56) 2-Year College Experience and 2-Year Graduate Experience (1 each)
	Least		
Family Income	Majority	Below Php 14,000 (27)	Below Php 14,000 (44)
	Least	Php 36,000 - 45,000 (2)	Php 46,000-60,000 (2)

Research Insights Through the Lens of Dervin's Sense-Making Theory

Looking at the above information through the lens of Brenda Dervin's Sense-making Theory leads the study to the following connections:

- PWDs actively seek sports information to fill gaps in their knowledge. The weak positive correlations between information-seeking behavior and sports participation suggest that while PWDs are making a way to bridge these gaps, other barriers (e.g., accessibility, financial constraints, social influence) limit the effectiveness of these efforts.

- PWDs use social media as a primary tool to bridge information gaps due to its accessibility and then support it with verified information from news and broadcast sources. However, the limited presence of sports information in mainstream media and inconsistent organizational support create continuing gaps that are challenging to overcome.

- The support from family, friends, and other factors, significantly influence PWDs' motivation and participation in sports. It shows the impact of social support to an individual's sense-making process. This is consistent with Dervin's theory, which says that personal connections and environmental factors are critical in constructing meaningful experiences.
- The different barriers faced by PWDs (discouragement from family, lack of support, lack of role models, lack of reliable leadership and support, economics, etc.) contribute to their slow progress in appreciating the sports information they get and acting on these in order to get the benefits of being in sports.
- Dervin's theory shows that the gap between PWDs and sports participation may be helped by bridging it through better sports information by creating effective and more widely circulated, better-planned information campaigns, establishing stronger support from different social and public organizations, as well as making relatable role models more visible.

The foregoing results proved the hypotheses of this research and supported the envisioned significance of this study.

Data from this study can be useful to policy makers, officers in public positions and individuals involved in private organizations to make more effective interventions for PWDs to get interested in sports and increase their sports participation.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This research substantiated the hypotheses that PWDs who actively seek sports information have a higher likelihood of participating in sports, and that several factors affect their decision to engage in it.

Direct relationships between several related factors supported this. Despite the weak positive results, the data are considered statistically significant to warrant being considered as a basis for further studies on the same matter or related issues. It proves that:

- The higher consumption of sports information contributes to the likelihood of their sports participation. It also showed its contribution in helping them stay in sports.
- The influence of family, friends and community are present when making life decisions, such as participating in sports
- Money also bears down on their decision to participate in sports
- Most respondents agreed that there is a need for better, more available and accessible sports information for PWDs
- There was a strong, positive opinion supporting the need for sport participation for all

The research also revealed that PWDs prefer using social media to obtain sports information but rely on traditional media to verify it.

Having two distinct clusters in the study, provided a textured look into what helped some of them to get into sports and what barriers have negatively impacted others' decision to participate in sports.

Conclusion

The results of this research successfully answered the research questions posted at the onset of this study.

Data show varied level of participation and sports information seeking among the participants and yet, the same data show consistent replies on their support for better availability of better-quality sports information, their strong opinion on the importance of sports among PWD and that family bears the most influence on people when taking decisions like participating in sports. This answers the first and third research question: "What is the level of information- seeking behavior of the PWDs in NCR towards sports?," as well as "What is the level of sports participation among PWDs in NCR?"

The foregoing also answered the second research question seeking the sense-making factors affecting the information-seeking behavior of the PWDs in NCR towards sports. Results also showed that following the "family," friends, personal knowledge and social opinion influence one's decisions in sports participation, as well as general decisions in life. Money concerns are also a big influence in deciding whether to join sports or not.

One of the objectives of this research was to examine the possible relationship between PWDs' sports information seeking behavior to their sports participation. It is also the fourth research question. Although the data revealed a weak positive correlation between variables in several data categories, the results were statistically significant indicating that the observed relationship is unlikely due to chance, and thus can be used as basis for further research or action.

The results show that while the relationship between sports information seeking behavior and sports participation among PWDs is modest, it is still definitely present and meaningful.

This insight can provide valuable guidance into possible approaches that can be taken to help increase PWDs' participation in sports. This relationship can also be put to good use by stakeholders and interested parties to develop means to better support PWD engagement and participation in sports.

Recommendations

Data mined from this research is significant and useful. This research can be used as a basis for positive actions for our PWDs.

With the envisioned significance of this study in mind, the following recommendations are proposed:

Further Research

- Use this study as groundwork research for further research which can dig deeper on the subject with a bigger sample and more rigorous methodology
- Explore related topics for research like:
 - A study on the impairment-specific implications of sports information seeking and participation of PWDs so that peculiarities may be effectively applied to communication efforts for each category
 - Longitudinal studies which track long-term impact of sports information and support systems on sports participation
 - Barrier analysis on different obstacles faced by different sub-groups in the PWD community to tailor-fit more effective plans and policies
 - A study on the preferred and effective platforms to disseminate validated sports information
 - The study can also have broader application by expanding it to also help increase participation in sports for the general population

For the Community

- Raise awareness and change perceptions
 - Organize community campaigns and events to raise awareness about the capabilities and achievements of PWDs in sports.
 - Challenge stereotypes and promote the idea that physical disabilities do not limit one's potential to succeed in sports or other areas of life.

- Provide information to more community members to raise awareness and underscore the importance of family and community support to PWDs' decision-making and sense of self.
- Support diverse roles for PWDs in sports at the community level
 - Encourage the inclusion of PWDs in various roles in sports within the community, such as athletes, coaches, officials, mentors, and advocates
 - Provide training and resources to help PWDs develop the skills needed to excel in these roles
 - Establish mentorship programs that connect PWD athletes with experienced sports professionals and peers. These networks can provide guidance, encouragement, and support, helping PWDs to overcome challenges and thrive in their sports pursuits
- Facilitate partnerships with PWD Advocacy groups
 - Partner with PWD advocacy groups to create more opportunities for their involvement in sports, help bridge gaps in access, provide support networks, and advocate for policy changes at the local and national levels.
- Celebrate achievements of PWDs
 - Recognize and celebrate the achievements of PWD athletes in community events, local media, and sports ceremonies.
 - Highlight their stories as sources of inspiration and proof that success in sports is attainable regardless of physical abilities

For Schools, Media, Support Organizations and Groups

- Improve information accessibility and quality

- Increase availability of sports information by developing comprehensive and accessible information resources tailored for PWDs
- Utilize different media platforms to disseminate information, with special attention to maximizing social media
- Ensure that information being shared/provided are accurate, up-to-date, and provides wide coverage of topics as well as information on opportunities for PWD participation
- Collaboration between different media outlets and national organizations (both public and private) to upgrade the quality and frequency of sports information available to PWDs
- Initiate comprehensive advocacy campaigns to raise awareness and support for PWD sports at national and local levels
- Establish and, if available, maximize use of social media platforms of organizations to increase information visibility in social media
- Strengthen social support systems
 - Leverage social networks
 - Encourage key influencers like family, friends, coaches and the community to help motivate PWDs to participate in sports,
 - Provide training and support to these key influencers to help them provide PWDs with support and encouragement
 - Develop community programs and initiatives that bring PWDs, their families and the broader community to sports
 - Create mentorship programs, PWD athletes can guide and inspire
- Connect with bigger organizations

- Establish connections with bigger organizations or concerned national-level agencies to either source or disseminate information in consistent frequency and quality, and a bigger scope
- Role model visibility
 - Make sports ambassadors out of successful PWD athletes and make them visible in media, especially social media (basing on results) to inspire others to get into sports
 - Highlight the benefits of, and opportunities in, sports through stories of PWD athletes

For the Government

- Push for development of more effective legislation or policies
 - Advocate for policies that promote inclusivity and equal opportunities for PWDs in sports
 - Encourage concerned government agencies to provide a wider range of services and efforts to promote sports among PWDs
 - Develop long-term strategic plans for PWDs with clear goals and objectives to address structural and leadership challenges
 - Put in place considerations for sustainability that can withstand changes in organizational leadership in both public and private groups
- Provide stronger support for agencies mandated to take care of PWDs in sports
- Establish support structures that will be consistently available for PWDs, independent of administration in power

- Use different government platforms, especially social media sites, to provide better quality, more frequently released and reliable information on PWDs in sports
- Utilize People with Disability Offices in Cities and Municipalities to help disseminate information on sports among PWDs in their area so that even inactive sports information seekers would be reached by information

The foregoing recommendations are submitted to enhance the participation in sports of PWDs specifically, and the whole population in general, by leveraging the power of information.

These insights underscore the importance of directed programs, targeted actions and support systems to enhance sports participation among PWDs. The study's results show the need for further research to explore these dynamics in greater depth, and to develop strategies, policies and initiatives to overcome the identified barriers.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX A

Quantitative Results and Analysis

***Presented as referred to in the manuscript**
(Tables 1-6 presented in the manuscript)

Table 7. *Level of Sports Participation among PWDs in NCR in terms of Interest in Participating in Sports.*

		N	Median	Std. Deviation
With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports?	Non-sports Inclined	73	3.0000	1.3993
With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports?	Sports Inclined	101	5.0000	1.0546

Table 7 shows the level of sports participation among PWDs in NCR in terms of interest in participating in sports. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the median computed is 3.00 with an interpretation of neutral, which signifies that generally, the respondents who are not into sports are neutral on having interest in joining sports. On the other hand, for sports inclined, the median computed is 5.00 with an interpretation of strongly agreeing. This means that generally, the respondents who are into sports are strongly agreeing that they have interest in joining sports.

Table 8. *Level of Sports Participation among PWDs in NCR.*

Group	What is your level of sports participation?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	0 - none at all	16	21.9178
	1- spectator	12	16.4384
	2 - play and movement	26	35.6164
	3 - hobby	16	21.9178
	4 - career	3	4.1096
	Total		73
Sports Inclined	0 - none at all	3	2.9703
	1- spectator	0	0.0000
	2 - play and movement	20	19.8020
	3 - hobby	19	18.8119
	4 - career	59	58.4158
	Total		101

Table 8 positions the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of sports participation. As shown, for non-sports inclined, the majority of the sample are in the level of play and movement with 26 respondents. On the other hand,

the least portion are in the level of career with three respondents. While for the sports inclined, the majority are in the level of career with 59 respondents, and the least portion are not in any level at all with only three respondents.

Table 9. *Level of Sports Participation among PWDs in NCR in terms of Length of Time being Active in Sports.*

Group	For how long have you been active in sports?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	Not Applicable	50	68.4932
	between 5 to 10 years	9	12.3288
	less than 5 years	9	12.3288
	more than 10 years	5	6.8493
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	Not Applicable	2	1.9802
	between 5 to 10 years	36	35.6436
	less than 5 years	33	32.6733
	more than 10 years	30	29.7030
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 9 depicts the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of sports participation in terms of length of time being active in sports. As shown, for non-sports inclined, the majority of the sample answers were not applicable with 68 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion are active for sports for more than 10 years with 13 respondents. While for the sports inclined, the majority are active in sports for less than 5 years with 36 respondents, and the least portion answered none with only two respondents.

Table 10. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Usual Consumption Of Sports Information In a Day.*

Group	How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours)	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	1 to 2 hours	28	38.3562
	3 to 4 hours	3	4.1096
	half an hour	41	56.1644
	more than 5 hours	1	1.3699
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	1 to 2 hours	55	54.4554
	3 to 4 hours	12	11.8812
	half an hour	27	26.7327
	more than 5 hours	7	6.9307
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 10 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of usual consumption of sports information in a day. As shown, for non-sports inclined, the majority of the sample are consuming sports information in a day for half an hour with a total of 41 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion consumes more than 5 hours with only one respondent. While for the sports inclined, the majority is consuming sports information in a day for 1-2 hours with 55 respondents, and the least portion consumes more than 5 hours with only seven respondents.

Table 11. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Frequency In Interaction With Sports Information.*

Group	What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought) interaction with sports information?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	Daily	10	13.6986
	Every other day	9	12.3288
	Once a month or less	21	28.7671
	Once a week	19	26.0274
	Twice a week	14	19.1781
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	Daily	53	52.4752
	Every other day	20	19.8020
	Once a month or less	5	4.9505
	Once a week	9	8.9109
	Twice a week	14	13.8614
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 11 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of frequency in interaction with sports information. As shown, for non-sports inclined, the majority of the sample are consuming sports information for one a month or less with 21 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion consumes every other day with 9 respondents. While for the sports inclined, the majority is consuming sports information daily with 53 respondents, and the least portion consumes one a month or less with only five respondents.

Table 12. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Actively Seeking Sports Information.*

Group	Do you actively seek sports information?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	No	28	38.3562
	Yes	45	61.6438
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	No	5	4.9505
	Yes	96	95.0495
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 12 demonstrates the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of actively seeking sports information. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with a total of 73 respondents. While for the sports inclined, majority answered yes also with a total of 96 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents who are actively seeking sports information from the sample of sports inclined.

Table 13. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Effect Of Sports Information In Deciding To Participate In Sports Or Not.*

Group	Do you think that the sports information you have affected your decision to participate in sports, or not?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	It was a part of my decision	0	0.0000
	No	18	24.6575
	Yes	55	75.3425
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	It was a part of my decision	31	30.6931
	No	27	26.7327
	Yes	43	42.5743
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 13 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of the effect of sports information in deciding to participate in sports or not. As shown, for non-sports inclined, the majority of the sample answered yes with 55 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion answered no with 18 respondents. While for the sports inclined, majority stated yes with 43 respondents, and the least portion stated no with 27 respondents.

Table 14. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of State Of Sports Information As Encouragement To Participate In Sports But Also Received Discouragement From The People Around Them.*

Group	Have you ever been inspired by the sports information you got, and later on discouraged by people around you? (family, friends, community, etc.)	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	No	27	36.98 63
	Yes	46	63.01 37
	Total	73	100.0 000
Sports Inclined	No	31	30.69 31
	Yes	70	69.30 69
	Total	101	100.0 000

Table 14 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of state of sports information as encouragement to participate in sports but also received discouragement from the people around them. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with a total of 46 respondents. While for the sports inclined, majority answered yes also with a total of 70 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample who experienced the state of sports information as encouragement to participate in sports but also received discouragement from the people around them.

Table 4. *Spearman Rho Correlation Testing between the PWD's Information-seeking Behavior and Level of Participation in Sports in NCR wherein The Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information as Independent Variable.*

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Do you actively seek sports information?	With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in	0.398 3	< .00 1	Weak Positive	Significant

	participating in sports?				
Do you actively seek sports information?	What is your level of sports participation?	0.3475	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
Do you actively seek sports information?	For how long have you been active in sports?	0.1780	0.0188	Very Weak Positive	Significant

Table 4 positions the results for the correlational testing employed between the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of actively seeking sports information and the level of their participation in sports in NCR, using the Spearman Rho as the data are treated in ordinal or ranked level. As shown, the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of actively seeking sports information have significant relationships in all the factors of level of participation in sports such as the interest in participating sports, sports participation and length of being active in sports, given that all of their p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = 0.0188, < 0.001$). Specifically in describing the type of relationships they have, the level of actively seeking sports information and level of interest in participating in sports have a weak positive relationship. Positive relationship means direct relationship wherein the movement of the two variables involved are in the same manner. And the weak aspect constitutes to the degree of manners of the relationship. With that, this means that as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Furthering, the level of actively seeking sports information and level of sports participation have weak positive relationships as well. This signifies that as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the level of sports information of the respondents also increases in a weak manner. Lastly, the level of actively seeking sports information and length of being active in sports have weak positive relationships. This means that as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases in a weak manner.

Table 5. Spearman Rho Correlation Testing between the PWD's Information-seeking Behavior and Level of Participation in Sports in NCR wherein the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a Day as Independent Variable.

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours)	With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports?	0.3410	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours)	What is your level of sports participation?	0.2798	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant

How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours)	For how long have you been active in sports?	0.1785	0.0185	Very Weak Positive	Significant
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Table 12 depicts the results for the correlational testing employed between the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of length of consumption of sports information in a day and the level of their participation in sports in NCR, using the Spearman Rho as the data are treated in ordinal or ranked level. As shown, the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of length of consumption of sports information in a day have significant relationships in all the factors of level of participation in sports such as the interest in participating sports, sports participation and length of being active in sports, given that all of their p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = 0.0021, < 0.001$). Specifically in describing the type of relationships they have, the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of interest in participating in sports have a weak positive relationship. Positive relationship means direct relationship wherein the movement of the two variables involved are in the same manner. And the weak aspect constitutes the degree of manners of the relationship. With that, this means that as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Moreover, the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of sports participation have weak positive relationships as well. This signifies that as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the level of sports information of the respondents also increases in a weak manner. Lastly, the length of consumption of sports information in a day and length of being active in sports have a very weak positive relationship. This means that as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the length of being active in sports also increases in a very weak manner.

Table 6. Spearman Rho Correlational Testing between the PWD's Information-seeking Behavior and Level of Participation in Sports in NCR wherein Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information as Independent Variable.

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Rho	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought) interaction with sports information	With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports?	0.3879	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant
What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought)	What is your level of sports participation?	0.3571	< .001	Weak Positive	Significant

interaction with sports information What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought) interaction with sports information	For how long have you been active in sports?	0.1626	0.0320	Very Weak Positive	Significant
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Table 6 demonstrates the results for the correlational testing employed between the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of frequency of interaction with sports information and the level of their participation in sports in NCR, using the Spearman Rho as the data are treated in ordinal or ranked level. As shown, the PWD's information-seeking behavior in terms of frequency of interaction with sports information have significant relationships in all the factors of level of participation in sports such as the interest in participating sports, sports participation and length of being active in sports, given that all of their p-values are less than 0.05, the accepted margin of error of the study ($p = < 0.001$). Specifically in describing the type of relationships they have, the frequency of interaction with sports information and level of interest in participating in sports have a weak positive relationship. Positive relationship means direct relationship wherein the movement of the two variables involved are in the same manner. And the weak aspect constitutes the degree of manners of the relationship. With that, this means that as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Moreover, the frequency of interaction with sports information and level of sports participation have weak positive relationships as well. This signifies that as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the level of sports information of the respondents also increases in a weak manner. Lastly, the frequency of interaction with sports information and length of being active in sports have a very weak positive relationship. This means that as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases in a very weak manner.

Table 15. *Level of Sports Participation among PWDs in NCR in terms of Thinking that Sports Information was a Factor in Pushing them to participate in Sports.*

Group	Do you think that sports information was a factor in pushing you to participate in sports?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	No	5	6.8493
	Yes	68	93.1507
	Total	73	100.000

Group	Do you think that sports information was a factor in pushing you to participate in sports?	Frequency	Percent
Sports Inclined	No	5	4.9505
	Yes	96	95.0495
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 15 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of sports participation in terms of thinking that sports information was a factor in pushing them to participate in sports. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with 68 respondents. While for the sports inclined, the majority answered yes also with 96 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample who think that the sports information was a factor in pushing them to participate in sports.

Table 16. *Factors for Consideration before Deciding to do anything (Watching a movie, eat out, do physical activities, hang out, etc.) of the Respondents.*

Descriptive Statistics

		Valid	Mode
[Family]	Non-sports Inclined	73	1
[Family]	Sports Inclined	101	1
[Friends]	Non-sports Inclined	73	2
[Friends]	Sports Inclined	101	2
[Social opinion]	Non-sports Inclined	73	3
[Social opinion]	Sports Inclined	101	3
[What you see on media]	Non-sports Inclined	73	4
[What you see on media]	Sports Inclined	101	4
[What you personally know about the topic]	Non-sports Inclined	73	5
[What you personally know about the topic]	Sports Inclined	101	5

Table 16 depicts the ranking of the factors involved for the consideration before deciding to do anything (watching a movie, eat out, do physical activities, hang out, etc.) of the respondents. As shown, majority of the respondents in terms of computing for the mode of the responses stated that they consider before deciding to do anything like watching a movie, eat out, do physical activities, hang out, etc., first is their family, second is their friends, third is the social opinion, fourth is what they see in social

media and lastly is what they personally know about the topic. This goes the same for both non-sports and sports inclined samples.

Table 17. *Factors that Have the Most Possibility to push the Respondents to do Something New*

Descriptive Statistics		Valid	Mode
[Family]	Non-sports Inclined	113	1
[Family]	Sports Inclined	101	1
[Friends]	Non-sports Inclined	113	2
[Friends]	Sports Inclined	101	2
[Social opinion]	Non-sports Inclined	113	5
[Social opinion]	Sports Inclined	101	3
[What you see on media]	Non-sports Inclined	113	4
[What you see on media]	Sports Inclined	101	4
[What you personally know about the topic]	Non-sports Inclined	113	5
[What you personally know about the topic]	Sports Inclined	101	5

Table 17 demonstrates the ranking of the factors that have the most possibility to push the respondents to do something new. As shown, majority of the respondents in terms of computing for the mode of the responses stated that they consider having the most possibility to push them to do something new for non-sports inclined sample is, first their family, second is their friends, fourth is what they see on social media and lastly are the social opinion and what they personally know about the topic. On the other hand, for the sports inclined sample, they consider first their family also, second is their friends, third is the social opinion, fourth is what they see in social media and lastly is what they personally know about the topic.

Table 18. *Factors that the Respondents think is most important to consider when making a Choice in their Lives*

Descriptive Statistics		Valid	Mode
[Family]	Non-sports Inclined	101	1
[Family]	Sports Inclined	113	1
[Friends]	Non-sports Inclined	101	3
[Friends]	Sports Inclined	113	2

Descriptive Statistics

		Valid	Mode
[Social opinion]	Non-sports Inclined	101	4
[Social opinion]	Sports Inclined	113	3
[What you see on media]	Non-sports Inclined	101	4
[What you see on media]	Sports Inclined	113	4
[What you personally know about the topic]	Non-sports Inclined	101	2
[What you personally know about the topic]	Sports Inclined	101	5

Table 18 presents the ranking of what the respondents think is most important to consider when making a choice in their lives. As shown, majority of the respondents in terms of computing for the mode of the responses stated that they consider most important when making a choice in their lives for non-sports inclined sample is, first their family, second is what they personally know about the topic, third is their friends, and lastly are the social opinion and what they see on social media. On the other hand, for the sports inclined sample, they consider first their family, second is their friends, third is the social opinion, fourth is what they see on social media and lastly is what they personally know about the topic.

Table 19. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in terms of Family Income Range*

Group	What is your estimated monthly FAMILY income range?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	14,000 to 25,000	14	19.1781
	26,000 to 35,000	14	19.1781
	36,000 to 45,000	2	2.7397
	46,000 to 60,000	4	5.4795
	61,000 above	12	16.4384
	below 14000	27	36.9863
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	14,000 to 25,000	35	34.6535
	26,000 to 35,000	12	11.8812

Group	What is your estimated monthly FAMILY income range?	Frequency	Percent
	36,000 to 45,000	3	2.970 3
	46,000 to 60,000	2	1.980 2
	61,000 above	5	4.950 5
	below 14000	44	43.56 44
	Total	101	100.0 000

Table 19 depicts the frequency and percentage of the respondents in terms of family income range. As shown, in the sample of non-sports inclined, the majority of them are within the family income range of below Php 14,000 which is a total of 27 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion of the sample are within the family income range of Php 36,000 – 45,000 which is only two respondents. As presented in the sample of sports inclined, the majority of them are within the family income range of below Php 14,000 as well, which is a total of 44 respondents. While, the least portion of the sample are with a family income range of Php 46,000 – 60,000 which is only two respondents.

Table 20. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Perceiving Sports Information As Beneficial*

Group	Do you think sports information is beneficial?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	No	5	6.849 3
	Yes	68	93.15 07
	Total	73	100.0 000
Sports Inclined	No	1	0.990 1
	Yes	100	99.00 99
	Total	101	100.0 000

Table 20 positions the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of perceiving sports information as beneficial. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with 68 respondents. While for the sports inclined, the majority answered yes also with 100 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample who perceive sports information as beneficial.

Table 21. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of State Of Sports Information As Useful For Them*

Group	Do you think the sports information you have seen so far, whether actively sought or not, were useful to you?	Frequen cy	Percent
Non- sports Inclined	No	16	21.91 78
	Yes	57	78.08 22
	Total	73	100.0 000
Sports Inclined	No	6	5.940 6
	Yes	95	94.05 94
	Total	101	100.0 000

Table 21 positions the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of state of sports information as useful for them. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with a total of 57 respondents. While for the sports inclined, majority answered yes also with a total of 95 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample who experienced the state of sports information as useful for them.

Table 22. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Perceiving Current Sports Information Available These Days Are Enough About Sports and PWDs*

Group	Do you think there us enough information available (online or books/magazines, etc) about sports and PWDs?	Frequen cy	Percent
Non- sports Inclined	No	32	43.83 56
	Yes	41	56.16 44
	Total	73	100.0 000
Sports Inclined	No	33	32.67 33
	Yes	68	67.32 67

Group	Do you think there us enough information available (online or books/magazines, etc) about sports and PWDs?	Frequency	Percent
Total		101	100.000

Table 22 depicts the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of perceiving current sports information available these days about sports and PWDs. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with a total of 41 respondents. While for the sports inclined, majority answered yes also with a total of 68 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample who perceive current sports information available these days being enough about sports and PWDs.

Table 23. *Level of Sports Participation among PWDs in NCR in terms of Thinking that the Sports Information must be more available for PWDs*

Group	Do you think we must have more sports information available for PWDs?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	No	3	4.1096
	Yes	70	95.8904
	Total	73	100.000
Sports Inclined	No	2	1.9802
	Yes	99	98.0198
	Total	101	100.000

Table 23 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of sports participation in terms of thinking that the sports information being more available for PWDs. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with 70 respondents. While for the sports inclined, the majority answered yes also with 99 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample who think that the sports information must be more available for PWDs.

Table 24. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Preferred Platform To Use In Seeking Sports Information*

Group	What platform do you prefer to use to seek sports information?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	Books/Research work	4	5.4795
	Newspaper	3	4.1096
	Social media	55	75.3425
	TV/Radio	11	15.0685
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	Books/Research work	14	13.8614
	Newspaper	2	1.9802
	Social media	74	73.2673
	TV/Radio	11	10.8911
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 24 demonstrates the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of preferred platform to use in seeking sports information. As shown, for non-sports inclined, the majority of the sample prefers social media with 855 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion preferred newspapers with only three respondents. While for the sports inclined, the majority prefers social media with 74 respondents, and the least portion prefers newspapers with only two respondents.

Table 25. *Level of Sports Participation among PWDs in NCR in terms of Recommending to other PWDs to be involved in Sports*

		N	Median	Std. Deviation
With 1 being the lowest, 5 being the highest, would you recommend other PWDs to be involved in sports?	Non-sports Inclined	73	5.0000	1.4241
With 1 being the lowest, 5 being the highest, would you recommend other PWDs to be involved in sports?	Sports Inclined	101	5.0000	0.9389

Table 25 demonstrates the level of sports participation among PWDs in NCR in terms recommending to other PWDs to be involved in sports. As shown for both non-sports

and sports inclined, the median computed is 5.00 with an interpretation of strongly agreeing, which signifies that generally, the respondents are strongly agreeing that they want to recommend to other PWDs to be involved in sports indeed whether they may be in non-sports or sports inclined samples.

Table 26. Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in their Level of Information-seeking Behavior in terms of Perceiving Sports Information To Be More Available to the PWDs

Group	Do you think sports information must be more available, especially to PWDs?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	No	7	9.5890
	Yes	66	90.4110
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	No	3	2.9703
	Yes	98	97.0297
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 26 depicts the frequency and percentage of the respondents regarding their level of information-seeking behavior in terms of perceiving sports information to be more available to the PWDs. As shown, for the non-sports inclined, the majority answered yes with a total of 66 respondents. While for the sports inclined, majority answered yes also with a total of 98 respondents. As observed, there is a higher number of respondents in the non-sports inclined sample who perceive sports information to be more available for PWDs.

Table 27. Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in terms of Age

Group	Age	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	8-13	3	4.11
	14 - 19	9	12.33
	20 - 25	3	4.11
	26 - 30	4	5.48
	31 - 35	10	13.70
	36 - 40	8	10.96
	41 - 45	8	10.96
	46 - 50	14	19.18
	51 above	14	19.18
	Total	73	100.00
Sports Inclined	8-13	0	0.00
	14 - 19	8	7.92
	20 - 25	17	16.83
	26 - 30	6	5.94

Group	Age	Frequency	Percent
	31 - 35	10	9.90
	36 - 40	13	12.87
	41 - 45	18	17.82
	46 - 50	14	13.86
	51 above	15	14.85
	Total	101	100.00

Table 27 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents in terms of age. As shown, in the sample of non-sports inclined, the majority of them are 46-50 and 51 and above years old with a total of 14 respondents each. On the other hand, the least portion of the sample are 8-13 and 20-25 years old which is only three respondents each. As presented in the sample of sports inclined, the majority of them are 41-45 years old which is a total of 18 respondents. While, the least portion of the sample are 26-30 years old which is only six respondents.

Table 28. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in terms of Gender.*

Group	Gender	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	Female	47	64.38
	Male	26	35.62
	Total	73	100.00
Sports Inclined	Female	39	38.61
	Male	62	61.39
	Total	101	100.00

Table 28 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents in terms of gender. As shown, in the sample of non-sports inclined, the majority of them are female with a total of 47 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion of the sample are male which is 26 respondents. As presented in the sample of sports inclined, majority of them are male which is a total of 62 respondents. While, the least portion of the sample are female which is 39 respondents.

Table 29. *Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment.*

Group	Up to what level did you reach in school?	Frequency	Percent
Non-sports Inclined	2 Year College	0	0.0000
	2 Year Course Graduate	0	0.0000
	College	29	39.7260
	College Undergraduate	6	8.2192
	Elementary	17	23.2877

Group	Up to what level did you reach in school?	Frequency	Percent
	Graduate School	17	23.2877
	High School	25	22.1239
	Sped	2	2.7398
	Sped Prevoc	1	0.8850
	Senior High School	0	0.0000
	Vocational Course	1	0.8850
	Total	73	100.0000
Sports Inclined	2 Year College	1	0.9901
	2 Year Course Graduate	1	0.9901
	College	56	55.4455
	College Undergraduate	0	0.0000
	Elementary	5	4.9505
	Graduate School	7	6.9307
	High School	27	26.7327
	Sped	2	1.9802
	Sped Prevoc	0	0.0000
	Senior High School	1	0.9901
	Vocational Course	1	0.9901
	Vocational Commercial Cooking Course	0	0.0000
	Total	101	100.0000

Table 29 positions the frequency and percentage of the respondents in terms of highest educational attainment. As shown, in the sample of non-sports inclined, the majority of them graduate college with a total of 26 respondents. On the other hand, the least portion of the sample are SPED Prevoc, and with vocational courses with only one respondent each. As presented in the sample of sports inclined, majority of them graduated college also which is a total of 56 respondents. While, the least portion of the sample are with 2 year college experience, 2 year graduate experience with only one

Figure 5. Scatter Plotting between the Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information and Interest in Participating in Sports.

Figure 5 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the level of actively seeking sports information and interest in participating in sports. As shown, as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 6. Scatter Plotting between the Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information and Sports Participation.

Figure 6 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the level of actively seeking sports information and sports participation. As shown, as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the sports participation also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 7. Scatter Plotting between the Level of Actively Seeking Sports Information and Length of being Active in Sports.

Figure 7 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the level of actively seeking sports information and length of being active in sports. As shown, as the level of actively seeking sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases but in a very weak manner.

Figure 8. Scatter Plotting between the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a day and Level of Interest in Participating in Sports.

Figure 8 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of interest in participating in sports. As shown, as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the level of interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 9. Scatter Plotting between the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a day and Sports Participation.

Figure 9 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the length of consumption of sports information in a day and level of sports participation. As shown, as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the level of sports participation also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 10. Scatter Plotting between the Length of Consumption of Sports Information in a day and Length of being Active in Sports.

Figure 10 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the length of consumption of sports information in a day and length of being active in sports. As shown, as the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, the length of being active in sports also increases but in a very weak manner.

Figure 11. Scatter Plotting between the Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information and Level of Interest in Participating in Sports.

Figure 11 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the frequency of interaction with sports information and level of interest in participating in sports. As shown, as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the level of interest of the respondents in participating also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 12. Scatter Plotting between the Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information and Sports Participation.

Figure 12 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between frequency of interaction with sports information and level of sports participation. As shown, as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the level of sports participation also increases but in a weak manner.

Figure 13. Scatter Plotting between the Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information and Length of being Active in Sports.

Figure 13 serves as a visual representation of the relationship between the frequency of interaction with sports information and length of being active in sports. As shown, as the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, the length of being active in sports also increases but in a very weak manner.

Replies to Open-Ended Questions in the Form

Table 31. Reasons One decided to Participate or Not in Sports

If you are not involved in sports, why did you decide not to participate in sports? OR If you are involved in sports, why did you decide to participate in sports?	
In Sports	Not in Sports
Health	Busy as a housewife and mother, work, other stuff
Become fit	No chance to practice
Strengthen body to move freely	Lack of attention
Socialization	Not interested
For information	Conflict of schedule with work
Time Management	Need to prioritize tasks and time
Not to be bored	Because of my disability/brittle bones
“Dahil kung gusto ko ang isang bagay ipagpapatuloy ko ito”	Time restrictions
Friends	Psychological issues
Lessen pressure on academics	Physical issues
Teacher in MAPEH recommended to join sports	“I am busy earning money”/ “I have to work. Not enough funds”
Personal satisfaction and happiness	Not good at sports
Improve my skills	Struggle to get along with people, socializing and gaining too much attention
To prompt my physical movement and exercise my mental capacity	I can't go alone

“I am a polio victim and I want to prove to myself that I can do something in sports like chess and shooting basketball”
 Acquire vital social skills, gain independence become empowered to act as an agent of change
 Helps develop life skills
 Hobby

Age
 Not an interest
 “I’m a tricycle driver”

Top answers: Health, Socialization, Sense of self-fulfillment

Top answers: Busy, Physical limitations, Not a priority

Table 32. *Top 3 Reasons to be Involved in Sports*

Whether you are in sports or not, what would be your top 3 reasons to be involved in sports?

Health
 Socialization
 Skills development
 Fitness
 Strength
 Improve my sports talent
 Meet new people/friends
 Learn more
 For her child to avoid gadgets
 Benefits
 Be active
 Hobby
 Free time
 Ease Boredom
 To win
 Leisure

Therapy
 Requirement
 Entertainment
 Physically Active
 Improve mental Health
 Employment
 Inspiration
 Inclusivity
 Help me financially
 To try new/other things/discover new skills
 Change of mindset
 Reduce anxiety and depression
 Avoiding bullying
 Self-fulfillment in achieving goals
 Happiness

Top replies: Health, Socialization, Mental Health

ANNEX B

Quantitative Results Summary

Demographic

Table 1: Age Distribution

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (28 respondents): Ages 46-50 and 51+
 - Least (3 respondents): Ages 8-13 and 20-25
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (18 respondents): Ages 41-45
 - Least (6 respondents): Ages 26-30

Table 2: Gender Distribution

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (47 respondents): Female
 - Least (26 respondents): Male
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (62 respondents): Male
 - Least (39 respondents): Female

Table 3: Educational Attainment

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (26 respondents): College Graduates
 - Least (1 respondent each): SPED Prevocational and Vocational Course
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (56 respondents): College Graduates
 - Least (1 respondent each): 2-Year College Experience and 2-Year Graduate Experience

Table 4: Family Income Range

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (27 respondents): Family income below Php 14,000
 - Least (2 respondents): Family income range Php 36,000 – 45,000
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (44 respondents): Family income below Php 14,000
 - Least (2 respondents): Family income range Php 46,000 – 60,000

Level of Information-seeking Behavior

Table 5: Actively Seeking Sports Information

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (73 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (96 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of respondents actively seeking sports information in the sports inclined sample.

Table 6: Usual Consumption of Sports Information in a Day

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (41 respondents): Half an hour
 - Least (1 respondent): More than 5 hours
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (55 respondents): 1-2 hours
 - Least (7 respondents): More than 5 hours

Table 7: Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (21 respondents): Once a month or less
 - Least (9 respondents): Every other day
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (53 respondents): Daily
 - Least (5 respondents): Once a month or less

Table 8: Perceiving Sports Information as Beneficial

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (68 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (100 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample perceiving sports information as beneficial.

Table 9: Perceiving Current Sports Information as Enough about Sports and PWDs

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (41 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (68 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample perceiving current sports information as enough about sports and PWDs.

Table 10: Preferred Platform to Use in Seeking Sports Information

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (85 respondents): Social media
 - Least (3 respondents): Newspaper
- **Sports Inclined**

- Majority (74 respondents): Social media
- Least (2 respondents): Newspaper

Table 11: Effect of Sports Information on Deciding to Participate in Sports

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (55 respondents): Yes
 - Least (18 respondents): No
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (43 respondents): Yes
 - Least (27 respondents): No

Table 12: State of Sports Information as Encouragement to Participate Despite Discouragement

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (46 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (70 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample experiencing encouragement despite discouragement.

Table 13: State of Sports Information as Useful

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (57 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (95 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of respondents in the sports inclined sample finding sports information useful.

Table 14: Perceiving Sports Information to Be More Available to PWDs

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (66 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (98 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of respondents in the non-sports inclined sample perceiving sports information to be more available for PWDs.

Factors Affecting Decision-making

Table 14: Factors Considered Before Deciding to Do Anything

- **Non-Sports Inclined and Sports Inclined (Same Ranking)**
 1. Family
 2. Friends
 3. Social opinion
 4. What they see on social media
 5. What they personally know about the topic

Table 15: Factors Most Likely to Push Respondents to Do Something New

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 1. Family
 2. Friends
 3. What they see on social media
 4. Social opinion and personal knowledge (tied for last)
- **Sports Inclined**
 1. Family
 2. Friends
 3. Social opinion
 4. What they see on social media
 5. What they personally know about the topic

Table 16: Most Important Factors When Making Choices in Life

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 1. Family
 2. Personal knowledge
 3. Friends
 4. Social opinion and what they see on social media (tied for last)
- **Sports Inclined**
 1. Family
 2. Friends
 3. Social opinion
 4. What they see on social media
 5. Personal knowledge

Level of Sports Participation

Table 17: Interest in Participating in Sports Among PWDs

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Median: 3.00 (Neutral interest in joining sports)
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Median: 5.00 (Strongly agreeing with having interest in joining sports)

Table 18: Level of Sports Participation

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (26 respondents): Level of play and movement
 - Least (3 respondents): Level of career
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (59 respondents): Level of career
 - Least (3 respondents): Not in any level

Table 19: Length of Time Active in Sports

- **Non-Sports Inclined**

- Majority (68 respondents): Not applicable
- Least (13 respondents): More than 10 years
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (36 respondents): Less than 5 years
 - Least (2 respondents): None

Table 20: Recommending Sports to Other PWDs

- **Non-Sports Inclined and Sports Inclined (Same Results)**
 - Median: 5.00 (Strongly agreeing that they want to recommend sports to other PWDs)

Table 21: Availability of Sports Information for PWDs

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (70 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (99 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of non-sports inclined respondents think sports information must be more available for PWDs.

Table 22: Influence of Sports Information on Participation

- **Non-Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (68 respondents): Yes
- **Sports Inclined**
 - Majority (96 respondents): Yes
 - Higher number of non-sports inclined respondents believe sports information was a factor in pushing them to participate in sports.

Relationship between Sports Information and Participation

Table 23: Correlation Between Actively Seeking Sports Information and Level of Sports Participation

- **Significant Relationships**
 - **Interest in Participating in Sports:** $p = 0.0188$
 - **Level of Sports Participation:** $p < 0.001$
 - **Length of Being Active in Sports:** $p < 0.001$
- **Type of Relationships**
 - **Interest in Participating in Sports:** Weak positive relationship
 - **Level of Sports Participation:** Weak positive relationship
 - **Length of Being Active in Sports:** Weak positive relationship
- **Interpretation**
 - As the level of actively seeking sports information increases, interest in participating, level of sports participation, and length of being active in sports all increase, but in a weak manner.

Table 24: Correlation Between Length of Consumption of Sports Information and Level of Sports Participation

- **Significant Relationships**
 - **Interest in Participating in Sports:** $p = 0.0021$
 - **Level of Sports Participation:** $p < 0.001$
 - **Length of Being Active in Sports:** $p < 0.001$
- **Type of Relationships**
 - **Interest in Participating in Sports:** Weak positive relationship
 - **Level of Sports Participation:** Weak positive relationship
 - **Length of Being Active in Sports:** Very weak positive relationship
- **Interpretation**
 - As the length of consumption of sports information in a day increases, interest in participating, level of sports participation, and length of being active in sports all increase, but mostly in a weak manner.

Table 25: Correlation Between Frequency of Interaction with Sports Information and Level of Sports Participation

- **Significant Relationships**
 - **Interest in Participating in Sports:** $p < 0.001$
 - **Level of Sports Participation:** $p < 0.001$
 - **Length of Being Active in Sports:** $p < 0.001$
- **Type of Relationships**
 - **Interest in Participating in Sports:** Weak positive relationship
 - **Level of Sports Participation:** Weak positive relationship
 - **Length of Being Active in Sports:** Very weak positive relationship
- **Interpretation**
 - As the frequency of interaction with sports information increases, interest in participating, level of sports participation, and length of being active in sports all increase, but mostly in a weak manner.

ANNEX C

Qualitative Results Final Themes

Figure 14. Thematic Analysis Summary of Themes

LEVEL OF SPORTS INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR OF PWDs	PLATFORMS PWDs PREFER TO USE MORE FOR SPORTS INFORMATION	FACTORS THAT AFFECT THE DECISION-MAKING OF PWDs IN SPORTS PARTICIPATION	RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPORTS INFORMATION AND PARTICIPATION OF PWDs	THE PRESENCE OF CHALLENGES IN CURRENT SPORTS INFORMATION FOR PWDs	THE ADDITIONAL EFFORTS NEEDED FOR PWDs ASIDE FROM FURTHERING SPORTS INFORMATION
<p>MAIN THEME 1 There Is Interest on Sports Information Among PWDs, But It Is Not Available Enough</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filipino PWDs are interested In Sports • Presence of National Organizations in Sports for PWDs • Lack of Availability of Sports Information for PWDs in Mainstream Platforms • The Need for More Consistent and Sustainable Efforts 	<p>MAIN THEME 2 The Usage of Various Media Platforms is Beneficial for the Dissemination of Sports Information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media is the Most Used Media Platform today for Sports Information • Easier Accessibility to Media Platforms helps to Further Information Dissemination 	<p>MAIN THEME 3 Factors Affecting the Sports Participation of PWDs are developed through Sports Information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion of PWDs into the Society through Organization and Government Efforts • The Influence of the Environment Surrounding the PWDs • The Aspirations of PWDs to be Valuable Members of the Society 	<p>MAIN THEME 4 The Significance of Progressing Sports Information for Higher Sports Participation of PWDs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing the Visibility of PWDs in Sports through Raising Awareness • Wider Sports Information can Also Increase Support and Resources Allocation for PWD Athletes • Accessibility of Sports Information in Media can Market the Availability of PWD Sports • The Presence of PWD Athletes in Media can Increase Encouragement for the Community 	<p>MAIN THEME 5 The Lack of Comprehensive Structure of Implementation for Long-term Development Goals for PWDs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Instability of Leadership Structure for Provision of Long-term Projects • The Lack of Information Campaigns for National Encouragement for PWDs • The Need for Stronger Foundation in Sports Advocacies for PWDs 	<p>MAIN THEME 6 The Need for Extensive Efforts Aside from Improving Sports Information for Sports Participation of PWDs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Significance of Further Research Studies in Relation to Sports Information and Participation of PWDs • Highlighting the Testimonials of PWD Athletes in Increasing the Efforts for Awareness and Advocacy

LEVEL OF SPORTS INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR OF PWDs

Main Theme 1: *There Is Interest on Sports Information Among PWDs, But It Is Not Available Enough*

Summary Table of Theme 1. Sub-themes and Codes for the Theme **There Is Interest on Sports Information Among PWDs, But It Is Not Available Enough**

Sub-themes	Codes
<p>Filipino PWDs are interested In Sports</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "There are people interested, but we had to really come up with money to be able to pay for their transportation." ● "Although they like the idea about this but not all of them will be able to get there." ● "Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work." ● "There are people that wanted to... but you had a market, but you had people that wanted to." ● "I was always a sports minded person... I played football, basketball." ● "It is hard if the information is zero. Even for elite athletes, information is important. Like getting techniques."
<p>Presence of National Organizations in Sports for PWDs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "For the time it was organized, and in fact the first participation of the country in the Paralympic Competition at that time, so that is where we started participating."

Lack of Availability of Sports Information for PWDs in Mainstream Platforms

- "Also the UN Convention on Person with Disabilities and sports started and it was ratified on May 2008."
- "If you check, this is only 15 years or 16 years to be exact."
- "Because the person with disabilities are their opportunities are less, in fact and often times. They are not well regarded in the mainstream or the person with the abilities."
- "So, if you're talking about how far is Philippines insofar as persons with disabilities in sports in terms of awareness, is I think 4. Because that's the reality."
- "The advocacy continues. It did not stop there. We continue. Unlike other countries advanced world like France... not to mention the United States."
- "In so far as the support of the agency to ensure that the awareness is given to the public to ensure that this person with disabilities will be given support and our information campaign towards a national level of awareness."
- "I am thinking if someone pays enough focus on para sports more potential athletes will know and get enticed to join. That will be a big help."
- "We have bountiful information available for regular sports but for para its is very limited."
- "We do not get the same attention. In Cordillera where I came from. The highlight is the success of 2023. But they only focus on regular. Like the achievement of the para athlete is higher because I got Gold in the Asian Level but I was not included in the "exceptional Cordillerans." I am not bitter, but I want to highlight my point with this as an example. If the researcher had more information, he would have understood and included that. The best way really is to incorporate more information about para sports in the regular news. Make it available for all."

The Need for More Consistent and Sustainable Efforts

- "However, the consistency and the sustainability of the program is very poor."
 - "I hope it can progress soon and we have officials who are also coming from that organization. But right now I have not seen a complete program towards it."
-

PLATFORMS PWDs PREFER TO USE MORE FOR SPORTS INFORMATION

Main Theme 2: *The Usage of Various Media Platforms is Beneficial for the Dissemination of Sports Information*

Summary Table of Theme 2. Sub-themes and Codes for the Theme of The Usage of Various Media Platforms are Beneficial for Dissemination of Sports Information.

Sub-themes	Codes
Social Media is the Most Used Media Platform today for Sports Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Socmed for me. Because if newspaper it's in English I cannot understand it fully. In social media it's easier understood. Both then and now." ● "For me it's social media ma'am. Because I always watch YouTube to learn more techniques about my sport. This helps me improve my performance." ● "Before I became an athlete there was still no socmed. I did not know I would be an athlete. I did not dream. I did not know I can be an athlete." ● "Not all skills you can learn from coaches, but if it is available then you get the information. I browse youtube for helpful tips" ● "Socmed since it's more accessible and understandable, but verify the info." ● "When you often see the information, this is especially true for me, like I always look at youtube I get idea and my knowledge increase. I always watch Michael Phelps on youtube for example." ● "Information will push us to participate." ● "But before I became an athlete there was still no socmed. I did not know I would be an athlete. I did not dream. I did not know I can be an athlete."
Easier Accessibility to Media Platforms helps to Further Information Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Mainstream for me, TV and radio. My reason is the credibility of the source of information. How reliable? If it's from TV, they make more effort to ensure the validity of the information. Then and now. Although socmed I also use, but I still verify." ● "Awareness is key, then next is to give them information and educate them to make these information available to them." ● "Once you create that kind of awareness, you of course you what we did is worse of course we have to use media."

FACTORS THAT AFFECT THE DECISION-MAKING OF PWDs IN SPORTS PARTICIPATION

Main Theme 3: *Factors Affecting the Sports Participation of PWDs are developed through Sports Information*

Summary Table of Theme 3. Sub-themes and Codes for the Theme of Factors Affecting the Sports Participation of PWDs are developed through Sports Information.

Sub-themes	Codes
Inclusion of PWDs into the Society through Private Organizations and Government Efforts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Accessibility is crucial. For example, in facilities like basketball and volleyball, what adjustments do they need to join?" ● "The tendency of PWDs is they want to be included." ● "Yes, they want to be included. If they are not included they feel left out and left behind." ● "The challenge is their common question if they will get support, like those coming from the provinces who will not be supported by LGUs." ● "Our thrust really is to make them aware. Not only in sports but information which matters to them." ● "The NCDA is under the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). The challenge with NCDA is funding, as the agency is small." ● "Actually, the first thing for us is information. If there is available information, at least a PWD will have an idea." ● "Awareness is key. We have to work for them to know about sports." ● "First, poverty. I believe at that time that when I got into sports, I'll be paying no money to the university." ● "During President Duterte's time, Para athletes got level allowances with the regular athletes and facilities were upgraded to be PWD friendly."
The Influence of the Environment Surrounding the PWDs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Your friends, your environment. Those are factors that will give you stamina to continue further." ● "Support from family comes in. So availability of information is really important." ● "My kids and my sons, my family, they were there to support." ● "Second is the influence of my coach. We call him Sensei. He gave us what life is all about, and I think that started it all."

**The Aspirations of
PWDs to be Valuable
Members of the
Society**

- "My passion to become a sports leader. It's like a pyramid. You have to put the bricks in one by one."
 - "President Ramos saw me... He gave me a verbal directive – form a national sports organization."
 - "Becoming aware was key for me to decide to become an athlete. I did not know before about para sports back then there was little information. But I am lucky I learned about this from friends."
 - "I learned about sports from my friend. I see them posting on social media and I was really inspired since they go to other places and countries."
 - "Sports as a whole definitely strengthen one's competitive spirit."
 - "You learn how to win. You learn how to lose."
 - "The spirit is already there. That helped me because the competitiveness was still there."
 - "Passion and Advocacy"
 - "Because of sports I was able to overcome my disability."
 - "In other words, it became my advocacy, my passion."
 - "I got so involved... it became a natural thing."
 - "The third is, of course, you have to believe in yourself."
 - "Your aspirations in life. What you want to do in life."
 - "I liked the challenge. I like winning."
 - "I am lucky that my husband was also very supportive. I experienced my family and neighbors belittling me saying I will not reach any where. But here I am in sports. I have seen many places already. I already have a house."
 - "There was a neighbor before who kept telling me I will not amount to nothing, later on I was thinking I cannot be limited to this. And now I have achieved a lot. My brothers are carpenters but they do not have a good house. Now we have a house. God changed my life thru sports."
 - "Also, Ma'am, the word inclusivity is important. We must be inclusive. We must not just be a token group since we also fight. It should be equal so that people could also see. There must also be highlight for para athletes."
 - "Sometimes Ma'am when I am competing, since we are all equal, we eat, we bathe, we go to the toilet, we
-

compete, I wonder why sometimes we do not get equal attention. They say inclusivity but its all lip service”

Funding as a Major Factor seen as affecting Sports Participation

- "Lack of funding is really a problem, especially when they compete abroad. Because if there is funding, it would be easier for them."
- "Awareness is the way to reach out to them. The downside is yes we have awareness, but then next is their question if they will get support."
- "The challenge is their common question if they will get support, like those coming from the provinces who will not be supported by LGUs."
- "The need for money is real we cannot deny that. But the love for sports is also real. It must be balanced."
- "Also the money I get from sports helps my family a lot."
- "There are people interested, but we had to really come up with money to be able to pay for their transportation."
- "Although they like the idea about this but not all of them will be able to get there."
- "Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work."
- When we formed it and I was asked by President Ramos to put together a national sports organization and linked up with the Olympic Committee, and so that we can be also provided funding. Obviously a very important requirement in being able to develop this part of sports or any sport for that matter.
- "Meaning to say, it has to do also with maybe all Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work. Work is more important than play or sport. Putting food on the table is the priority."

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPORTS INFORMATION AND PARTICIPATION OF PWDs

Main Theme 4: *The Significance of Progressing Sports Information for Higher Sports Participation of PWDs*

Summary Table of Theme 4. Sub-themes and Codes for the Theme of the Significance of Progressing the Sports Information for Higher Sports Participation of PWDs.

Sub-themes	Codes
Increasing the Visibility of PWDs in Sports through Raising Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Information is a big deal for me." ● "Sports information is actually one of the tools to promote para sports." ● "When the information is readily available publicly, it is easier to participate." ● "Once you create that kind of awareness, you most likely will increase participation." ● "Inclusivity is important. We must be inclusive." ● "There must also be highlight for para athletes." ● "Awareness must be given to the public to ensure that person with disabilities are given support. Our information campaign for awareness must be on a national level." ● "I was not really looking for the information but it passed through my feed. When I already see these, then I actively looked for them." ● "We always say that sports information is actually one of the tools to promote para sports." ● We have Magna Carta for person with disabilities aligned with the UN Convention. It is more campaign and awareness and to put more premiums in there in terms of program to enable them to be part of the society. you know, in fact there are many soldiers who have been, you know, injured and harmed, what with disabilities but only few has been integrated into the society because they they need a lot of medical attention, both psychologically, physically, mentally and even spiritually. So I think we need to have a total or holistic campaign to ensure that all the needs, not only in sports, I'm speaking but only requirement of the person because we call them Vulnerable sector right. ● "The information I found really helped me because it gave me ideas" ● "When the information is readily available publicly. It is easier to participate. It is easier to get an idea. When you see your idols on media you will have more

interest to also join because you will see the perks, the benefits.”

- “Because with personal experience, it (sports information) helped me and got me into sports.”
- “To sum it up, and this is from my years of being involved in sports, awareness is key.”

Wider Sports Information can Also Increase Support and Resources Allocation for PWD Athletes

- “It is good to be known because then you can get more support.”
- “You become more productive if you are thinking only about sports, because the resources are already there.”
- “If we look at the number actually, around 10% of Filipinos are PWDs.”
- “The best way really is to incorporate more information about para sports in the regular news. Make it available for all.”
- “If the information about the athlete is available, whether it's TV, radio, or social media, it is good for people to know the athletes.”
- “Sometimes it's just marketing. Even us in sports, we only give attention to people who already made it. Marketing for para sports is still not big. Although media outlets like RP2 do good, but the private sector can do more.”
- “One of the success of an athlete, is how other sectors support him.”
- “Information is a big deal for me. Like for an athlete like me, it is good to be known because then you can get more support. There will be sectors which will support what you are doing. This is specially true for starting athletes.”

Accessibility of Sports Information in Media can Market the Availability of PWD Sports

- “Especially for para sports. That is the difference or disparity. I see this. The promotion on para sports in other countries is better.”
 - “Marketing for para sports is still not big.”
 - “There are people who really do the promotion.”
 - “I am thinking if someone pays enough focus on para sports more potential athletes will know and get enticed to join.”
 - “You have to use media... print, radio, television... for the purpose of creating awareness about sport and physical fitness.”
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The Presence of PWD Athletes in Media can Increase Encouragement for the Community

- "Because when people see information about para sports, they are inspired to be involved and be like the athletes who have done it. Like those of us who live up the mountains and have no idea what is going on in the city. We do not know about para sports and when we see people like us who are in sports, we get an idea and we also want to be like them."
 - "When you see your idols on media you will have more interest to also join because you will see the perks, the benefits."
 - "It will also help para sports be more popular so it feeds each other."
 - "Sport in its own general way, has these values of fair play, teamwork, discipline, camaraderie, perseverance... applies to those with disability."
 - "Participation develops self-confidence, heightens self-esteem, and strengthens the competitive spirit of the person."
 - "I have the same opinion Ma'am. Because when people see information about para sports, they are inspired to be involved and be like the athletes who have done it."
 - "I used to see FB posts of my friends and province mates, and they are going to many places and some abroad. I also wanted to have the same experience. So yes information really helps. It helps us dream."
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THE PRESENCE OF CHALLENGES IN CURRENT SPORTS INFORMATION FOR PWDs

Main Theme 5: *The Lack of Comprehensive Structure of Implementation for Long-term Development Goals for PWDs*

Summary Table of Theme 5. Sub-themes and Codes for the Theme of the Lack of Comprehensive Structure of Implementation for Long-term Development Goals for PWDs.

Sub-themes	Codes
<p>The Instability of Leadership Structure for Provision of Long-term Projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "Changes in leadership in the PSC." ● "We don't have a long term sustainable program as part of our development goals."

**The Lack of
Information
Campaigns for
National
Encouragement for
PWDs**

- "Our medium development goals we also don't have in fact. So I think we need to make our foundation. I think it's the foundation which is lacking."
 - "Moving forward that it should be sustainable not only with the person with disabilities in sports, but also with the regular sports."
 - "The problem of both are equal in terms of Sustainability program because I think there we miss something on how to move forward to that level."
 - "What we need is to come up with our own table and talk about it. To ensure that both parties are given time to give their opinion, their expertise, or maybe we can invite experts to talk about it with the experience of our leaders."
 - "There's a need to ensure the leader should be able to address those matters."
 - "During the time of President Duterte was the time when the para athletes took equal allowance rates with the regular athletes. We were able to sustain that."
 - "It should be a holistic approach in all forms of giving the privileges and opportunities to the PWDs."
 - "The program, the facilities, the accessibility, the continuity of their needs and preparation for their campaign...."
 - "This is the reality, not only in the Philippines, but this is part of the studies of the UN Is that often times Persons with disabilities are giving less importance."
 - "We should promote the advocacy of trying to get the burdens of their disability into their abilities."
 - "Capacity building for this sector. We should give more emphasis on how they can contribute to our society."

 - "In so far as the program of the agency, our campaign on para sports, in partnership with the organization, it's not sufficient."
 - "I think we need to have more fora to discuss what are the things that should be done to be done and should be accomplished after."
 - "We need to identify why still we are here. Why we need to study or to get other opinions on how to move forward."
 - "It's not only about sports, we should also look into after sports life of para athletes."
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- "We should bridge the gap between their sports life and their future because they also have families."
 - "We have to expand our horizon in terms of how to give them the best opportunities."
 - "When we have expert information, we have guidance how to do it, how to get in, or find people who can help you, find local coaches who can teach you. When there are local events you can join. So its useful."

The Need for Stronger Foundation in Sports Advocacies for PWDs

- "I believe that Sport is one of the qualifying factors. It is a transformative tool to make the person with disabilities to be adopted into societies, because societies are biased against persons with disabilities."
- "Sports should be the right tool to bridge the gap for them to be socially included in society."
- "The adaptation of their abilities, both in communities, education or in the economic sector, or the benefits that sports can give to them will give them a lot of opportunities."
- "As we equal them with the regular athletes, they are now considered as equal in terms of making them members of the national team."
- "We have more support to the para athletes than to some NSAs national team of other sports."
- "I think it is more of campaign because we have so much law in the Philippines."
- "We need more information, we need more campaign, we need more program because some person with disabilities in their own mind they are not part of the sector which can help nation building given their disabilities."
- "We need to have a total or holistic campaign to ensure that all the needs, not only in sports, I'm speaking but all the requirements of the person."
- "I think as those in the vulnerable sector we want to protect them."
- "We are good in starting the policy but implementing afterwards and sustaining it is another thing and lacking."

THE ADDITIONAL EFFORTS NEEDED FOR PWDs ASIDE FROM FURTHERING SPORTS INFORMATION

Main Theme 6: *The Need for Extensive Efforts Aside from Improving Sports Information for Sports Participation of PWDs*

Summary Table of Theme 6. Sub-themes and Codes for the Theme of The Need for Extensive Efforts Aside from Improving Sports Information for Sports Participation of PWDs.

Sub-themes	Codes
<p>The Significance of Further Research Studies in Relation to Sports Information and Participation of PWDs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "In my experience in the PSC, for at least 20 years, that is one of my campaigns because research is the most important aspect of planning. Everything should start with research for us to have good policies to be implemented." ● "So far as research is concerned, I think it's nil in the PSC." ● "We pushed before that our Planning Division do more research which includes persons with disabilities, but I think they are not capable enough to make that campaign." ● "It's a matter of giving guidance to put the right direction, the leadership, and priorities of this agency." ● "There should be an awareness-related and permission campaign at the school level." ● "We are even trying to push that the Para sports also be included in the Palarong Pambansa but I think it is not yet finalized." ● "The National Council Disability Affairs, DILG, DSWD, and PSC should come together and come up with a common ground to have a holistic program." ● "Legislators are very supportive, especially right now. Our senators and congressmen are all sportsmen." ● "We need an honest-to-goodness campaign and information or awareness." ● "That is why your research is very timely. Maybe it can help us get more athletes."
<p>Highlighting the Testimonials of PWD Athletes in Increasing the Efforts for Awareness and Advocacy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● "One of the efforts will be a documentation of best practices to encourage them through stories or testimonies of other PWDs who successfully overcame challenges and became successful." ● "We can get information on what challenges they faced, how they overcame them, and what they did."

There will be affinity, unlike when we tell them about regular athletes."

- "The NCDA invites speakers from Philspada to speak. The PWDs connect with them. It is also for promotion. Testimonies are very effective."
 - "However, they can register with the DSWD. It is better for them to make them more legitimate. The SEC also is on. There are national federations which we require them to have SEC registration."
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ANNEX D

Coding Book For Qualitative Results

Figure 15. *Thematic Analysis Map*

Relationship between Sports Information and Participation

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"Information is a big deal for me."

"It is good to be known because then you can get more support."

"You become more productive if you are thinking only about sports, because the resources are already there."

"If the information about the athlete is available. Whether it's TV, radio or social media, it is good for people to know the athletes."

"In developed countries, they really have information on the athlete and the sports which we do not have much here."

"Especially for para sports. That is the difference or disparity. I see this. The promotion on para sports in other countries is better."

"There are people who really do the promotion."

Do you think it is important for sports information to be more accessible for PWDs to increase PWD participation?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"Sports information is actually one of the tools to promote para sports."

"If we only rely on games done by the PSC, for example, like the Philippine National Paragames, or even the Palarong Pambansa, it is not enough."

"We have bountiful information available for regular sports but for para it's very limited."

"I am thinking if someone pays enough focus on para sports more potential athletes will know and get enticed to join."

"The best way really is to incorporate more information about para sports in the regular news. Make it available for all."

"Inclusivity is important. We must be inclusive."

"There must also be highlight for para athletes."

"If we look at the number actually, around 10% of Filipinos are PWDs."

"Marketing for para sports is still not big."

Do you agree that when we actively seek sports information, the chances of going in sports is higher?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"When the information is readily available publicly. It is easier to participate."

"When you see your idols on media you will have more interest to also join because you will see the perks, the benefits."

"It will also help para sports be more popular so it feeds each other."

"It is hard if the information is zero."

"Even for elite athletes, information is important."

"Not all skills you can learn from coaches, but if it is available then you get the information."

Among the platforms, social media, TV, radio, magazine, books, and other platforms, which do you prefer to use? Before becoming an athlete and now?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"Socmed for me. Because if newspaper its in English I cannot understand it fully. In social media it's easier understood. Both then and now."

"Mainstream for me, TV and radio. My reason is the credibility of the source of information. How reliable? If it's from TV, they make more effort to ensure the validity of the information. Then and now. Although socmed I also use, but I still verify."

"For me it's social media ma'am. Because I always watch YouTube to learn more techniques about my sport. This helps me improve my performance."

"Before I became an athlete there was still no socmed. I did not know I would be an athlete. I did not dream. I did not know I can be an athlete."

"Socmed since it's more accessible and understandable, but verify the info."

What is the level of sports information seeking behavior of our PWDs?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"For the time it was organized, and in fact the first participation of the country in the Paralympic Competition at that time, so that is where we started participating."

"Also the UN Convention on Person with Disabilities and sports started and it was ratified on May 2008."

"If you check, this is only 15 years or 16 years to be exact."

"Because the person with disabilities are their opportunities are less, in fact and often times. They are not well regarded in the mainstream or the person with the abilities."

"So if you're talking about how far is Philippines insofar as persons with disabilities in sports in terms of awareness, is I think 4. Because that's the reality."

"The advocacy continues. It did not stop there. We continue. Unlike other countries advanced world like France... not to mention the United States."

"In so far as the support of the agency to ensure that the awareness is given to the public to ensure that this person with disabilities will be given support and our information campaign towards a National level of awareness."

"However, the consistency and the sustainability of the program is very poor."

"I hope it can progress soon and we have officials who are also coming from that organization. But right now I have not seen a complete program towards it."

You mentioned about consistency and sustainability. What would be one big factor in terms of these two things, which present challenges for us?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"Changes in leadership in the PSC."

"We don't have a long term sustainable program as part of our development goals."

"Our medium development goals we also don't have in fact. So I think we need to make our foundation. I think it's the foundation which is lacking."

"Moving forward that it should be sustainable not only with the person with disabilities in sports, but also with the regular sports."

"The problem of both are equal in terms of Sustainability program because I think there we miss something on how to move forward to that level."

"What we need is to come up with our own table and talk about it. To ensure that both parties are given time to give their opinion, their expertise, or maybe we can invite experts to talk about it with the experience of our leaders."

"There's a need to ensure the leader should be able to address those matters."

"During the time of President Duterte was the time when the para athletes took equal allowance rates with the regular athletes. We were able to sustain that."

"It should be a holistic approach in all forms of giving the privileges and opportunities to the PWDs."

"The program, the facilities, the accessibility, the continuity of their needs and preparation for their campaign...."

"This is the reality, not only in the Philippines, but this is part of the studies of the UN Is that often times Persons with disabilities are giving less importance."

"We should promote the advocacy of trying to get the burdens of their disability into their abilities."

"Capacity building for this sector. We should give more emphasis on how they can contribute to our society."

Well, this is an observation from the outside -- external communication or our information education Campaign (IEC) of the PSC as the sole government agency in sports. Do you think it's enough?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"In so far as the program of the agency, our campaign on para sports, in partnership with the organization, it's not sufficient."

"I think we need to have more fora to discuss what are the things that should be done to be done and should be accomplished after."

"We need to identify why still we are here. Why we need to study or to get other opinions on how to move forward."

"It's not only about sports, we should also look into after sports life of para athletes."

"We should bridge the gap between their sports life and their future because they also have families."

"We have to expand our horizon in terms of how to give them the best opportunities."

Could sports fill up the gap of your my participation. Do you think that sports can do that?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"I believe that Sport is one of the qualifying factors. It is a transformative tool to make the person with disabilities to be adopted into societies, because societies are biased against persons with disabilities."

"Sports should be the right tool to bridge the gap for them to be socially included in society."

"The adaptation of their abilities, both in communities, education or in the economic sector, or the benefits that sports can give to them will give them a lot of opportunities."

"As we equal them with the regular athletes, they are now considered as equal in terms of making them members of the national team."

"We have more support to the para athletes than to some NSAs national team of other sports."

"I think it is more of campaign because we have so much law in the Philippines."

"We need more information, we need more campaign, we need more program because some person with disabilities in their own mind they are not part of the sector which can help nation building given their disabilities."

"We need to have a total or holistic campaign to ensure that all the needs, not only in sports, I'm speaking but all the requirements of the person."

"I think as those in the vulnerable sector we want to protect them."

"We are good in starting the policy but implementing afterwards and sustaining it is another thing and lacking."

How about research? Do we have related research about this? Or anything related to PWDs or their participation?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"In my experience in the PSC, for at least 20 years, that is one of my campaigns because research is the most important aspect of planning. Everything should start with research for us to have good policies to be implemented."

"So far as research is concerned, I think it's nil in the PSC."

"We pushed before that our Planning Division do more research which includes persons with disabilities, but I think they are not capable enough to make that campaign."

"It's a matter of giving guidance to put the right direction, the leadership, and priorities of this agency."

"There should be an awareness-related and permission campaign at the school level."

"We are even trying to push that the Para sports also be included in the Palarong Pambansa but I think it is not yet finalized."

"The National Council Disability Affairs, DILG, DSWD, and PSC should come together and come up with a common ground to have a holistic program."

"Legislators are very supportive, especially right now. Our senators and congressmen are all sportsmen."

"We need an honest-to-goodness campaign and information or awareness."

As a former athlete Sir, what three factors or five factors that influenced you personally for you to enter into sports. What pushed you?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"First, poverty. I believe at that time that when I got into sports, I'll be paying no money to the university."

"Second is the influence of my coach. We call him Sensei. He gave us what life is all about, and I think that started it all."

"The third is, of course, you have to believe in yourself."

"Your friends, your environment. Those are factors that will give you stamina to continue further."

"Your aspirations in life. What you want to do in life."

"My passion to become a sports leader. It's like a pyramid. You have to put the bricks in one by one."

"Sports is not a part of the school curriculum. It is an extra skill that you have to learn outside of the school program."

In your opinion, does social media really matter, information when it comes to enticing PWDs to join sports?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"Nowadays socmed is really the big platform to entice them."

"PWDs really find it more accessible through social media."

"In the social media era, it's easier for them to get information."

"Awareness is key, then next is to give them information and educate them to make these information available to them."

"It is very timely to have this thesis. It is the first time that the PSC reached out to NCDA."

"For the longest time, sports is not a priority. We will have an event in July where PSC will give support. One of the topics will be disability and sports."

"It is a big thing that NCDA recognizes that awareness is very important."

What are the biggest factors in their life in making decisions?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"Actually, the first thing for us is information. If there is available information, at least a PWD will have an idea."

"Support from family comes in. So availability of information is really important."

"The tendency of PWDs is they want to be included."

"Yes, they want to be included. If they are not included they feel left out and left behind."

"Accessibility is crucial. For example, in facilities like basketball and volleyball, what adjustments do they need to join?"

"During President Duterte's time, Para athletes got level allowances with the regular athletes and facilities were upgraded to be PWD friendly."

"The NCDA is under the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). The challenge with NCDA is funding, as the agency is small."

Do you think, since in our economy sports is not a priority, more so for PWD in sports. However, do you think we should continue to push for their participation in sports?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"This is a common challenge for us here in the Philippines. In sports, they struggle for funding but when they are already winners they get the attention."

"So the government probably wonders what sports and PWDs can contribute to the economy or nation building?"

"Lack of funding is really a problem, especially when they compete abroad. Because if there is funding, it would be easier for them."

"Our thrust really is to make them aware. Not only in sports but information which matters to them."

"The challenge is their common question if they will get support, like those coming from the provinces who will not be supported by LGUs."

"Awareness is the way to reach out to them. The downside is yes we have awareness, but then next is their question if they will get support."

What other efforts do you think we can do in order to improve the number of PWDs participating in sports?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"One of the efforts will be a documentation of best practices to encourage them through stories or testimonies of other PWDs who successfully overcame challenges and became successful."

"We can get information on what challenges they faced, how they overcame them, and what they did. There will be affinity, unlike when we tell them about regular athletes."

"The NCDA invites speakers from Philspada to speak. The PWDs connect with them. It is also for promotion. Testimonies are very effective."

"However, they can register with the DSWD. It is better for them to make them more legitimate. The SEC also is on. There are national federations which we require them to have SEC registration."

Is if there were more information about paragames or the paralympics, would there be more participation?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"The first purpose or call it steps we not we will take based on our documents is that we would we need to create public awareness on sport..."

"Once you create that kind of awareness, you most likely will increase participation."

"It's important here in the beginning, is basic. Basic information, physical fitness, recreation and the value sports that people can play..."

"You have to use media... print, radio, television... for the purpose of, of creating awareness about sport and physical fitness."

"The first sport that actually used to create public awareness was wheelchair basketball. Why? Because it is basketball, and we're a basketball crazy country."

"Once you create public awareness, you have to create a venue for people to experience sports."

"As you increase awareness, you increase participation and you increase news and events."

"Think of a pyramid, the base is your foundation and has to move up to the top of the pyramid. The top of the pyramid is the elite."

"Your foundation or your base also grows... Philippine National Para Games... from grassroots to national, to sub-regional, regional, and international levels."

"Sport in its own general way, has these values of fair play, teamwork, discipline, camaraderie, perseverance... applies to those with disability."
"Participation develops self-confidence, heightens self-esteem, and strengthens the competitive spirit of the person."

**By observation, do you think Filipinos actively seek information on sports?
Like, do you think they actively, they actively use social media to find it?**

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"You look at some countries, they are so sports minded... the Philippine is not there yet."

"We rank in the middle, rank 4, 5, 6 in the southeast and that's been there for decades now."

"Work is more important than play or sport. Putting food on the table is the priority."

"Many... need to work and many you see them in the streets sometimes and maybe a very small number will consider sport."

"There are people interested, but we had to really come up with money to be able to pay for their transportation."

"Although they like the idea about this but not all of them will be able to get there."

"Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work."

"There are people that wanted to... but you had a market, but you had people that wanted to."

"I was always a sports minded person... I played football, basketball."

"It's really a very debilitating, a very difficult condition to be in."

What kept you in sports then sir?

Significant Phrases from Answers:

"Because of sports I was able to overcome my disability."

"Sports as a whole definitely strengthen one's competitive spirit."

"I liked the challenge. I like winning."

"You learn how to win. You learn how to lose."

"The spirit is already there. That helped me because the competitiveness was still there."

"My kids and my sons, my family, they were there to support."

"Eventually a few friends came up at that time when I was doing all that."

"President Ramos saw me... He gave me a verbal directive – form a national sports organization."

"I decided to try out blind sports. I had the first national blind games."

"In other words, it became my advocacy, my passion."

"I competed in Shotput and Javelin."

"I got so involved... it became a natural thing."

"I was the world President of USA. Then I sat in the board of the International Paralympic Committee."

"Awareness is key. We have to work for them to know about sports."

"We need to provide the information even to our lawmakers, even to our Sports commissioners."

FINALIZED QUALITATIVE RESULTS

LEVEL OF SPORTS INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR OF PWDs

MAIN THEME 1: There is Presence of Interest from the PWDs towards Sports Information but the Availability of it is not Enough

Sub-themes

Filipino PWDs are interested In Sports

"There are people interested, but we had to really come up with money to be able to pay for their transportation."

"Although they like the idea about this but not all of them will be able to get there."

"Filipinos would rather play, but sometimes they can't because they need to work."

"There are people that wanted to... but you had a market, but you had people that wanted to."

"I was always a sports minded person... I played football, basketball."

"It's really a very debilitating, a very difficult condition to be in."

Presence of National Organizations in Sports for PWDs

"For the time it was organized, and in fact the first participation of the country in the Paralympic Competition at that time, so that is where we started participating."

"Also the UN Convention on Person with Disabilities and sports started and it was ratified on May 2008."

"If you check, this is only 15 years or 16 years to be exact."

Lack of Availability of Sports Information in Mainstream Platforms

"Because the person with disabilities are their opportunities are less, in fact and often times. They are not well regarded in the mainstream or the person with the abilities."

"So if you're talking about how far is Philippines insofar as persons with disabilities in sports in terms of awareness, is I think 4. Because that's the reality."

"The advocacy continues. It did not stop there. We continue. Unlike other countries advanced world like France... not to mention the United States."

"In so far as the support of the agency to ensure that the awareness is given to the public to ensure that this person with disabilities will be given support and our information campaign towards a National level of awareness."

The Need for More Consistent and Sustainable Efforts

"However, the consistency and the sustainability of the program is very poor."
"I hope it can progress soon and we have officials who are also coming from that organization. But right now I have not seen a complete program towards it."

PLATFORMS PWDS PREFER TO USE FOR SPORTS INFORMATION

MAIN THEME 2: The Usage of Various Media Platforms are Beneficial for Dissemination of Sports Information

Sub-themes

Social Media is the Most Used Media Platform today for Sports Information

"Socmed for me. Because if newspaper its in English I cannot understand it fully. In social media it's easier understood. Both then and now."

"For me it's social media ma'am. Because I always watch YouTube to learn more techniques about my sport. This helps me improve my performance."

"Before I became an athlete there was still no socmed. I did not know I would be an athlete. I did not dream. I did not know I can be an athlete."

"Socmed since it's more accessible and understandable, but verify the info."

Easier Accessibility to Media Platforms helps to Further Information Dissemination

"Mainstream for me, TV and radio. My reason is the credibility of the source of information. How reliable? If it's from TV, they make more effort to ensure the validity of the information. Then and now. Although socmed I also use, but I still verify."

"Awareness is key, then next is to give them information and educate them to make these information available to them."

FACTORS THAT AFFECT THE DECISION-MAKING OF PWDS IN SPORTS PARTICIPATION

MAIN THEME 3: Factors Affecting the Sports Participation of PWDS are developed through Sports Information

Sub-themes

Inclusion to the Society of PWDS through Organization and Government Efforts

"Accessibility is crucial. For example, in facilities like basketball and volleyball, what adjustments do they need to join?"

"The tendency of PWDS is they want to be included."

"Yes, they want to be included. If they are not included they feel left out and left behind."

"The challenge is their common question if they will get support, like those coming from the provinces who will not be supported by LGUs."

"Our thrust really is to make them aware. Not only in sports but information which matters to them."

"The NCDA is under the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). The challenge with NCDA is funding, as the agency is small."

"Actually, the first thing for us is information. If there is available information, at least a PWD will have an idea."

"Awareness is the way to reach out to them. The downside is yes we have awareness, but then next is their question if they will get support."

"Awareness is key. We have to work for them to know about sports."

"First, poverty. I believe at that time that when I got into sports, I'll be paying no money to the university."

"Lack of funding is really a problem, especially when they compete abroad. Because if there is funding, it would be easier for them."

"During President Duterte's time, Para athletes got level allowances with the regular athletes and facilities were upgraded to be PWD friendly."

The Influence from the Environment Surrounding the PWDs

"Your friends, your environment. Those are factors that will give you stamina to continue further."

"Support from family comes in. So availability of information is really important."

"My kids and my sons, my family, they were there to support."

"Second is the influence of my coach. We call him Sensei. He gave us what life is all about, and I think that started it all."

"My passion to become a sports leader. It's like a pyramid. You have to put the bricks in one by one."

"President Ramos saw me... He gave me a verbal directive – form a national sports organization."

The Aspirations of PWDs to be Valuable members of the Society

"Sports as a whole definitely strengthen one's competitive spirit."

"You learn how to win. You learn how to lose."

"The spirit is already there. That helped me because the competitiveness was still there."

Passion and Advocacy

"Because of sports I was able to overcome my disability."

"In other words, it became my advocacy, my passion."

"I got so involved... it became a natural thing."

"The third is, of course, you have to believe in yourself."

"Your aspirations in life. What you want to do in life."

"I liked the challenge. I like winning."

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPORTS INFORMATION AND PARTICIPATION OF PWDs

MAIN THEME 4: The Significance of Progressing the Sports Information for Higher Sports Participation of PWDs

Sub-themes

Increasing the Visibility of PWDs in Sports through Raising Awareness

"Information is a big deal for me."

"Sports information is actually one of the tools to promote para sports."

"When the information is readily available publicly, it is easier to participate."

"Once you create that kind of awareness, you most likely will increase participation."

"Inclusivity is important. We must be inclusive."

"There must also be highlight for para athletes."

Wider Sports Information can Also Increase Support and Resources Allocation for PWD Athletes

"It is good to be known because then you can get more support."

"You become more productive if you are thinking only about sports, because the resources are already there."

"If we look at the number actually, around 10% of Filipinos are PWDs."

"The best way really is to incorporate more information about para sports in the regular news. Make it available for all."

"If the information about the athlete is available, whether it's TV, radio, or social media, it is good for people to know the athletes."

Accessibility of Sports Information in Media can Market the Availability of PWD Sports

"Especially for para sports. That is the difference or disparity. I see this. The promotion on para sports in other countries is better."

"Marketing for para sports is still not big."

"There are people who really do the promotion."

"I am thinking if someone pays enough focus on para sports more potential athletes will know and get enticed to join."

"You have to use media... print, radio, television... for the purpose of creating awareness about sport and physical fitness."

The Presence of PWD Athletes in Media can Increase Encouragement for the Community

"When you see your idols on media you will have more interest to also join because you will see the perks, the benefits."

"It will also help para sports be more popular so it feeds each other."

"Sport in its own general way, has these values of fair play, teamwork, discipline, camaraderie, perseverance... applies to those with disability."

"Participation develops self-confidence, heightens self-esteem, and strengthens the competitive spirit of the person."

"Not all skills you can learn from coaches, but if it is available then you get the information."

THE PRESENCE OF CHALLENGES IN CURRENT SPORTS INFORMATION FOR PWDs

MAIN THEME 5: The Lack of Comprehensive Structure of Implementation for Long-term Development Goals for PWDs

Sub-themes

The Instability of Leadership Structure for Provision of Long-term Projects

"Changes in leadership in the PSC."

"We don't have a long term sustainable program as part of our development goals."

"Our medium development goals we also don't have in fact. So I think we need to make our foundation. I think it's the foundation which is lacking."

"Moving forward that it should be sustainable not only with the person with disabilities in sports, but also with the regular sports."

"The problem of both are equal in terms of Sustainability program because I think there we miss something on how to move forward to that level."

"What we need is to come up with our own table and talk about it. To ensure that both parties are given time to give their opinion, their expertise, or maybe we can invite experts to talk about it with the experience of our leaders."

"There's a need to ensure the leader should be able to address those matters."

"During the time of President Duterte was the time when the para athletes took equal allowance rates with the regular athletes. We were able to sustain that."

"It should be a holistic approach in all forms of giving the privileges and opportunities to the PWDs."

"The program, the facilities, the accessibility, the continuity of their needs and preparation for their campaign...."

"This is the reality, not only in the Philippines, but this is part of the studies of the UN Is that often times Persons with disabilities are giving less importance."

"We should promote the advocacy of trying to get the burdens of their disability into their abilities."

"Capacity building for this sector. We should give more emphasis on how they can contribute to our society."

The Lack of Information Campaigns for National Encouragement for PWDs

"In so far as the program of the agency, our campaign on para sports, in partnership with the organization, it's not sufficient."

"I think we need to have more fora to discuss what are the things that should be done to be done and should be accomplished after."

"We need to identify why still we are here. Why we need to study or to get other opinions on how to move forward."

"It's not only about sports, we should also look into after sports life of para athletes."

"We should bridge the gap between their sports life and their future because they also have families."

"We have to expand our horizon in terms of how to give them the best opportunities."

The Need for Stronger Foundation in Sports Advocacies for PWDs

"I believe that Sport is one of the qualifying factors. It is a transformative tool to make the person with disabilities to be adopted into societies, because societies are biased against persons with disabilities."

"Sports should be the right tool to bridge the gap for them to be socially included in society."

"The adaptation of their abilities, both in communities, education or in the economic sector, or the benefits that sports can give to them will give them a lot of opportunities."

"As we equal them with the regular athletes, they are now considered as equal in terms of making them members of the national team."

"We have more support to the para athletes than to some NSAs national team of other sports."

"I think it is more of campaign because we have so much law in the Philippines."

"We need more information, we need more campaign, we need more program because some person with disabilities in their own mind they are not part of the sector which can help nation building given their disabilities."

"We need to have a total or holistic campaign to ensure that all the needs, not only in sports, I'm speaking but all the requirements of the person."

"I think as those in the vulnerable sector we want to protect them."

"We are good in starting the policy but implementing afterwards and sustaining it is another thing and lacking."

THE ADDITIONAL EFFORTS NEEDED FOR PWDs ASIDE FROM FURTHERING SPORTS INFORMATION

MAIN THEME 6: The Need for Extensive Efforts aside from Improving Sports Information for Sports Participation of PWDs

Sub-themes

The Significance of Further Research Studies in Relation to Sports Information and Participation of PWDs

"In my experience in the PSC, for at least 20 years, that is one of my campaigns because research is the most important aspect of planning. Everything should start with research for us to have good policies to be implemented."

"So far as research is concerned, I think it's nil in the PSC."

"We pushed before that our Planning Division do more research which includes persons with disabilities, but I think they are not capable enough to make that campaign."

"It's a matter of giving guidance to put the right direction, the leadership, and priorities of this agency."

"There should be an awareness-related and permission campaign at the school level."

"We are even trying to push that the Para sports also be included in the Palarong Pambansa but I think it is not yet finalized."

"The National Council Disability Affairs, DILG, DSWD, and PSC should come together and come up with a common ground to have a holistic program."

"Legislators are very supportive, especially right now. Our senators and congressmen are all sportsmen."

"We need an honest-to-goodness campaign and information or awareness."

Highlighting the Testimonials of PWD Athletes in Increasing the Efforts for Awareness and Advocacy

"One of the efforts will be a documentation of best practices to encourage them through stories or testimonies of other PWDs who successfully overcame challenges and became successful."

"We can get information on what challenges they faced, how they overcame them, and what they did. There will be affinity, unlike when we tell them about regular athletes."

"The NCDA invites speakers from Philspada to speak. The PWDs connect with them. It is also for promotion. Testimonies are very effective."

"However, they can register with the DSWD. It is better for them to make them more legitimate. The SEC also is on. There are national federations which we require them to have SEC registration."

ANNEX E

Questionnaire Form

SPORTS INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR AND SPORTS PARTICIPATION AMONG PWDS

Hello! Thank you for participating in this brief survey.

I am Emmalyn Bamba, a student of the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU), taking up a Master in Development Communication course.

This study aims to better understand information need and use of differently-abled people, in the light of their sports information seeking behavior and sports participation.

After successfully presenting this as a thesis in UPOU, the results and findings of this small research will be shared with policy makers, communicators and sports leaders. We hope to push them to make changes in policies and efforts to increase sports participation and sports information consumption among people with different abilities.

As a PWD, or what we call Super Human in the sports community, your input are important information which will help us understand the relationship, if any, between sports information and the participation of PWDS in sports.

Should you wish to answer the online questionnaire instead, here is the link <https://forms.gle/j2nqyCsoCEA3VjsW6>
Or you may message me at _____ so I can send you the clickable link
Maraming salamat po muli sa inyong paglahok! :)

*required information

PART 1

1. Name (optional): _____

2. *Age (mark only one):

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> 8 - 13 | <input type="radio"/> 36 - 40 |
| <input type="radio"/> 14 - 19 | <input type="radio"/> 41 - 45 |
| <input type="radio"/> 20 - 25 | <input type="radio"/> 46 - 50 |
| <input type="radio"/> 26 - 30 | <input type="radio"/> 51 above |
| <input type="radio"/> 31 - 35 | |

3. *Which region do you reside in? (Please mark only one)

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="radio"/> National Capital Region (NCR) | <input type="radio"/> Region 7 - Central Visayas |
| <input type="radio"/> Cordillera Administrative Region (CAR) | <input type="radio"/> Region 8 - Eastern Visayas |
| <input type="radio"/> Regional 1 - Ilocos | <input type="radio"/> Region 9 - Zamboanga Peninsula |
| <input type="radio"/> Region 2 - Cagayan Valley | <input type="radio"/> Region 10 - Northern Mindanao |
| <input type="radio"/> Region 3 - Central Luzon | <input type="radio"/> Region 11 - Davao |
| <input type="radio"/> Region 4A - Calabarzon | <input type="radio"/> Region 12 - Soccsksargen |
| <input type="radio"/> Region 4B MIMAROPA - Southwestern Tagalog | <input type="radio"/> Region 13 - Caraga |
| <input type="radio"/> Region 5 - Bicol | <input type="radio"/> BARMM - Bangsamoro |
| <input type="radio"/> Region 6 - Western Visayas | |

4. *Gender Male Female

5. *Up to what level did you reach in school? (encircle one please)

Elementary

High School

College Graduate School

N/A

6. *What is your estimated monthly FAMILY income range?

- below 14000
- 14,000 to 25,000
- 26,000 to 35,000
- 36,000 to 45,000
- 46,000 to 60,000
- 61,000 above

PART 2 – DECISION FACTORS

PAKI BASA PO MUNA NG MAIGI ANG INSTRUCTIONS BEFORE ANSWERING THIS SECTION.

Please mark one column only once.
Column 1 = most influential, HIGHEST
Column 5 = least influential, LOWEST

Please rank the choices in the following three questions according to their importance to you. Paki rank po mula pinaka maimpluwensya (1), hanggang pinaka mababa ang impluwensya (5). SALAMAT PO.

7. *Factors you consider before you decide to do anything (example: watch a movie, eat out, do physical activities, hang out, etc.) mark 1 to 5, **1 as the highest & 5 lowest**

- Family
- Friends
- Social Opinion
- What you see on media
- What you personally know about the topic

8. *What factors have the most possibility to push you to do something new? mark 1 to 5, **1 as the highest & 5 lowest**

- Family
- Friends
- Social Opinion
- What you see on media
- What you personally know about the topic

9. *What factors do you think is most important to consider when making a choice in your life?

mark 1 to 5, **1 as the highest & 5 lowest**

- Family
- Friends
- Social Opinion
- What you see on media
- What you personally know about the topic

PART 3 – SPORTS INFORMATION SEEKING

10. *Do you think sports information is beneficial

- Yes
- No

11. *Do you actively seek sports information?

- Yes
- No

12. **If your answer is YES in #11**, please answer this: Where do you usually SEARCH for sports information? Multiple answers allowed, check all that applies.

- Social Media
- Newspaper
- Books/Research work
- TV/ Radio

13. **If your answer is NO in #11**, please answer this: Where do you usually COME ACROSS sports information? Multiple answers allowed, check all that applies.

- Social Media
- Newspaper
- Books/Research work
- TV/ Radio

14. *How long do you usually consume sports information in a day? (in hours) mark only one.

- half an hour
- 1 to 2 hours
- 3 to 4 hours
- more than 5 hours

15. *What is the frequency of your conscious (you actively sought) interaction with sports information? Mark only one.

- Daily
- Every other day
- Twice a week
- Once a week
- Once a month or less

16. *Do you think there is enough information available (online or books/magazines, etc.) about sports and PWDs?

- Yes
- No

17. *What platform do you prefer to use is seeking sports information? *

- Social media
- Newspaper
- Books/Research work
- TV/Radio

PART 4 – PROCESSING INFORMATION

18. *Do you think that the sports information you have affected your decision to participate or not to participate in sports?

- Yes
- No

19. *Have you ever been inspired by the sports information you got, and later on discouraged by people around you? (family, friends, community, etc.)

- Yes
- No

20. *Do you think the sports information you have seen so far, whether actively sought or not, were useful to you ?

- Yes
- No

21. *Do you think sports information must be more available, especially to PWDs?

Yes

No

PART 5 – SPORTS PARTICIPATION

22. *With 1 as lowest and 5 highest, what is your interest in participating in sports? _____

23. *What is your level of sports participation? Mark only 1 oval.

0 - none at all

1- spectator

2 - play and movement

3 - hobby

4 - career

24. *Have you ever been involved in sports in any capacity? Please choose as much as applies

athlete

coach / trainer

administrative staff

management officer

Spectator/supporter/fan

NOT INVOLVED

25. *For how long have you been active in sports?

NOT APPLICABLE

less than 5 years

between 5 to 10 years

more than 10 years

26. *With 1 being the lowest, 5 being the highest, would you recommend other PWDs to be involved in sports?

1

2

3

4

5

PART 6 – SHARE YOUR THOUGHTS!

A few words will go a long way in making us understand ways we can improve our present situation.

This is the last part 😊

27. *Do you think sports is important to PWDs?

Yes

No

28. *Do you think we must have more sports information available for PWDs?

Yes

No

29. *Do you think that sports information was a factor in pushing you to participate OR not participate in sports?

Yes

No

30. *If you **are not involved** in sports, why did you decide not to participate in sports?

OR If you **are involved** in sports, why did you decide to participate in sports?

31. *Whether you are in sports or not, what would be your top 3 reasons to be involved in sports?

THANK YOU for participating!!! Your contribution to this small effort will go a long way in helping us understand where we can improve the way sports information is delivered, presented and made available to you and others. Please be assured that all information shared in this survey will be handled with utmost confidentiality, care and respect. **God bless you!**
